

RI4C2
Research & Innovation
For Cities & Citizens

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First FOREU2 Report on “practices and measures taken/to be taken to ensure the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in R&I long-term strategies”

Report

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I. Executive Summary

This joint deliverable aims at addressing the issue of Gender Equality in R&I via case studies taken from 16 H2020 SwafS projects awarded to European University Alliances. The purpose is to share measures (already implemented or ongoing) at university or at Alliances levels to ensure the mainstreaming of Gender Equality in R&I long-term strategies. The case studies serve as good practices to inspire individual universities and Alliances to make continuous progress in this area.

The deliverable first presents an overview of the participant universities and of the policy framework for Gender Equality within R&I institutions in particular and more globally within the European Union. Each case study is then described in details. Finally, the last section outlines the main findings drawn out from all case studies and offers recommendations for possible measures to be implemented to improve the mainstreaming of Gender Equality in R&I.

II. Mainstreaming the Gender Dimension in R&I long-term strategies

A. Overview of European Universities

The 24 Alliances of European Universities that have received funding at the 2020 Erasmus+ Pilot Call related to the European Universities initiative have joined forces within a second Forum of European Universities: FOREU2. It is within this framework that this deliverable is written. Indeed, this is a joint deliverable that was included in the work plan of 13 out of 22 H2020 SwafS projects awarded to European University Alliances. The concerned Alliances/SwafS projects are:

- Aurora/Aurora RI
- Circle U./Circle U. ERIA
- EC2U/RI4C2
- EELISA/EELISA innoCORE
- ENHANCE/ENHANCERIA
- ENLIGHT/ENLIGHT RISE
- ERUA/Re:ERUA
- EURECA-PRO/RE-EURECA-PRO
- NeurotechEU/NeurotechRI
- RUN-EU/RUN-EU PLUS
- Transform4Europe/T4ERI
- UNITA/Re-UNITA
- UNIVERSHEH/Beyond UNIVERSEH

This first joint deliverable is a report on “practices and measures taken/to be taken to ensure the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in R&I long-term strategies”. Each Alliance that had included this deliverable in their work plan has provided (at least) one case study on this topic. Some Alliances have submitted more than one case study, and it was decided that all case studies submitted would be included in this deliverable, as it provides a greater diversity of examples that can serve as good practices and lead to thorough recommendations. Moreover, some Alliances that did not have this deliverable included in their work plan decided to contribute and submitted a case study. This concerns the following Alliances/SwafS projects: EUNICE/REUNICE, FilmEU/FilmEU_RIT and UNIC/UNIC4ER.

All case studies present in detail the objectives, implementation, successes and challenges of the chosen activity related to Gender Equality. A majority of them provide individual recommendations in relation to the case study presented. The case studies and their associated recommendations are summarised in a fourth section, with the aim to offer general recommendations for the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in R&I long-term strategies.

B. Importance of mainstreaming the Gender dimension

This deliverable is in direct link with the Transformation Module n°2, part of the Horizon 2020 Work Programme 2020 update – part 16 “Science with and for Society (SwafS)” and its Other Action 33 “Support for the Research and Innovation Dimension of European Universities (Part II)”. Transformation Module n°2 specifically states that “strengthening human capital, enabling balanced brain circulation and gender balance” is a key element of the R&I area.

Therefore, all SwafS projects had the possibility to include the question of Gender Equality in R&I in their work plan. As this topic was taken up by all Alliances in their SwafS project, it was a natural consequence to prepare this joint deliverable. Indeed, collecting case studies from various Alliances (whether at university or at Alliance levels), provides examples of good practices that can serve as a reference for individual universities and Alliances in order to foster the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in current and future R&I activities and projects. By doing so, FOREU2 and its member Alliances are fulfilling their part as role models.

C. Policy framework for Gender Equality

The promotion of equality between women and men is a priority for the European Union (EU), in all its activities, as required by the Treaties. Gender Equality is a core value of the EU, a fundamental right¹ and key principle of the *European Pillar of Social Rights*². Additionally, Gender Equality is an essential condition for economic growth as far as it brings more productivity and it would lead to an increase in EU GDP per capita by 6.1 to 9.6%, which amounts to €1.95 to €3.15 trillion³.

Therefore, since 1996, the European Commission aims at integrating the mainstreaming of Gender Equality in all policies in order to eliminate any gender inequalities using various policy documents and measures. For instance, the European Commission adopted the Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025⁴ where the objectives and gender mainstreaming actions are proposed at the European level to reach significant progress by 2025, including in the R&I field. The strategy proposes a series of measures to foster Gender Equality in the Horizon Europe Framework Programme; for example, through the mandatory Gender Equality Plan (GEP) from applying institutions.

Moreover, other policy documents on Gender Equality in the European Research Area (ERA) aim at reaching the objectives for Gender Equality in R&I: for instance, the policy document “A new ERA for Research and Innovation”⁵ includes actions to develop, since 2021, inclusive GEPs with Member States and stakeholders to promote Gender Equality within the EU in R&I. In addition,

¹ Articles 2 and 3(3) TEU, Articles 8, 10, 19 and 157 TFEU and Articles 21 and 23 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights.

² European pillar of social rights - Publications Office of the EU (europa.eu)

³ Economic Benefits of Gender Equality in the European Union | European Institute for Gender Equality (europa.eu)

⁴ Gender Equality strategy (europa.eu)

⁵ <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52020DC0628&from=EN>

the [She Figures](#) were also published in 2021 to monitor the state of Gender Equality in R&I across Europe.

The “European Research Area Policy Agenda – Overview on action for the period 2022–2024”⁶ also underlines the importance of promoting Gender Equality and the need of gender mainstreaming as it was noted in the *Ljubljana Declaration on Gender Equality in R&I* in 2021.

Thus, this joint deliverable supports those policy developments and aims at providing concrete examples that can be used to foster the work on Gender Equality in R&I within individual universities and Alliances.

⁶ European Research Area Policy Agenda (europa.eu)

III. Case studies within European Universities

A. Case study 1: Aurora Alliance

1. Summary

The University of Iceland has a dedicated committee, entitled the 'equal rights committee.' The committee's purpose is to oversee equality in a broad sense and, as stated by article 65 of the constitution of Iceland, to have Gender Equality at the forefront of its work. The Equal Rights Committee works in an advisory capacity to the University Council on equality and diversity-related issues. The Committee has several upcoming projects which may be considered case studies for the SwafS projects.

2. Description

The Division of Human Resources is responsible for ensuring that all staff, regardless of sex or gender, receive the same salary for the same or equivalent work (cf. Article 6 of Act no. 150/2020 and Article 9 of Act no. 86/2018).

The Equality officer in consultation with the pro-rector for science have provided support for research into gendered finance for example by being part of the ACT project on gender budgeting in research organisations.

The Equality officer and the programme coordinator for gender studies have a long-time collaboration to encourage students on courses in applied gender studies to complete projects on the operations of schools, faculties, and central administration.

School public relations managers, in collaboration with research institutes focusing on equality, run a programme to highlight research on issues of equality using diverse and accessible methods, for example through lectures or videos or by making equality research results accessible on the UI website.

The following examples are especially relevant for science and innovation:

- The Equal Rights Committee of UI is launching an **equality and diversity education programme in the fall of 2023** where a section will be dedicated to the importance of implementing a **gendered vision in research**. The programme includes a video presentation by an expert for researchers, training them to consider the gender/equality dimension from the study design stage to the dissemination of results.
- The Equal Rights Committee of UI, in collaboration with the Doctoral Student Association of UI, runs a programme **with the goal of increasing collaboration among postgraduate students writing theses about equality** matters by creating a forum for collaboration between postgraduate students at different schools whose projects relate to equality.
- The Division of Human Resources has a project aimed at evaluating and responds to the **impact of the COVID-19 pandemic** on the University community, with a **focus on**

marginalised groups and intersecting forms of discrimination. The idea is to map the overall impact on staff and develop proposals. E.g., increased burden due to changes in teaching arrangements and in co-operation with Pro-rector for science to **find ways to evaluate the gendered consequences** on the productivity of academic staff and propose ways to correct these.

3. Contact Point

Ulce Equality Officer: Sveinn Guðmundsson, sveinn@hi.is

Aurora Contact Point: Auður Inga Rúnarsdóttir, air@hi.is

4. References

https://english.hi.is/university/committees_and_councils#:~:text=The%20Equal%20Rights%20Committee%20of,the%20forefront%20of%20its%20work.

B. Case study 2: CIRCLE U. Alliance

Circle U. and the University of Pisa

1. Summary

The University of Pisa has made significant progress in terms of Gender Equality politics in the last years:

It has elaborated its **Gender Equality Plan**;

It has founded the **Equity and Diversity Office (EDO)** with the aim to set up, implement, monitor and evaluate all the politics for Gender Equality, inclusivity, work and well-being;

EDO also possesses missions of support and organisational coordination, administration management, and technical-scientific expertise for all subjects and political bodies carrying out gender policies within the University and the institution of **Free anti-violence centre** (Sportello interuniversitario pisano contro la violenza di genere). This aims at identifying and managing discrimination and gender-based violence cases and, in particular, to provide a counselling/assistance/rights information service. This Centre is the first free anti-violence centre created from the collaboration between three different universities that are University of Pisa, Sant'Anna School of advanced Studies and Scuola Normale Superiore.

2. Description

a) Context

The University of Pisa is a public institution with 20 departments, 17 Libraries and 13 Museums. It offers a big number of programmes such as 61 Bachelor's degree, 71 Master's degree and 36 PhD programmes. The University's context is variegated, as it is composed by a large and composite community from all over Italy and abroad.

Inside the institution, the Committee on Equal Opportunities, Wellness of Employees and Non-Discrimination (in brief: CUG) operates with the scientific and managerial support of the Equality and Diversity Office (in brief: EDO). The CUG promotes Gender Equality and focuses its actions on different strategic objectives for inclusion, valorisation of differences, leadership balance, data collection, gender budgeting and wellbeing in workplaces. The CUG moves itself and works based on the regulatory framework outlined at national level and, of course, at the European level. In particular, the University of Pisa, through the CUG and EDO, elaborates its strategies in accordance with the National Code of Equal Opportunities between Women and Men (2006), in implementation of the Law 183/2010 and in accordance with the measures introduced by the Law 162/2021. The University of Pisa has made important efforts to advance Gender Equality and inclusion through the elaboration of positive action plans with the aim to identify problems, discriminations and gaps. In these terms, a significant role is played by the Gender budgeting, realised each year, to monitor the situation and highlight both positive and negative trends. Among the positive ones: there is a good resource allocation to the CUG; the governance's support in the co-construction of politics and a strong research activity in which gender is adopted as a category of analysis using an intersectional approach. Among the negative trends, has been registered the underrepresentation of women in leadership managerial positions and in full professorships. This shows how the process towards a complete Gender Equality is complex despite being a core value of the University of Pisa.

b) Objectives

The University of Pisa has elaborated its Gender Equality Plan (GEP), which represents the long-term strategy to ensure the mainstreaming of the gender dimension. Inside the GEP are defined the practices and measures to achieve the goals.

The objectives fixed by our university are different and multiple. Here follows a list organised in five main thematic areas of intervention:

1) WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE

- Promoting work-life balance policies aimed at creating an inclusive working environment respectful of differences and characterised by organisational well-being
- Adopting measures to help reconciling activity and load of caring responsibilities for the University community
- Promoting health and safety in the workplace through risk assessment from a gender perspective

2) GENDER BALANCE IN LEADERSHIP AND DECISION-MAKING

- Fostering the structural change through the analysis of the university sources of law to identify possible interventions fostering the gender representation

3) GENDER EQUALITY IN RECRUITMENT AND CAREER PROGRESSION

- Fostering a progressive gender balance in the composition of the teaching staff

4) MEASURES AGAINST GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE, INCLUDING SEXUAL HARASSMENT

- Institution of a free anti-violence centre to identify and manage discrimination and gender-based violence cases

5) INTEGRATION OF THE GENDER DIMENSION INTO RESEARCH AND TEACHING CONTENT; FOSTERING AND DISSEMINATING GENDER EQUALITY ALSO THROUGH THE PUBLIC ENGAGEMENT

- Integrating the gender perspective into research and teaching content, enhancing the gender awareness in an interdisciplinary dimension
- Activation of the Postgraduate Programme in "Gender Studies and Policies"

c) Implementation

The state of GEP's implementation is in line with the planning as it is reported in the **annual monitoring document** written by the Equity and Diversity Office (EDO) and approved last 21st June 2023 by the Academic Senate and the Board of Directors of the University. This document is part of a big Report titled *Piano Integrato delle Attività e Organizzazione (PIAO)*, required by the Law 80/2022, which represents the governance's action plan and programming activities of the organisation concerning several focuses such as: performance; Gender Equality; anticorruption; staff requirements.

d) Successes

Below the principal successes reported since the beginning (January 2022) of the implementation of the Gender Equality Plan of the University of Pisa:

- Institution of the **Equity and Diversity Office (EDO)**, which provides the subjects, involved in the GEP implementation with practical support and tools; cooperates with and involve the stakeholders at all levels to ensure the implementation of the GEP measures; raises awareness on advantages accruing from Gender Equality in universities and assess progress towards Gender Equality.
- Institution of a **Free anti-violence centre** (*Sportello interuniversitario pisano contro la violenza di genere*) to identify and manage discrimination and gender-based violence cases and, in particular, it provides a counselling/assistance/ rights information service. This Centre is the first free anti-violence centre created from the collaboration between three different universities that are University of Pisa, Sant'Anna School of advanced Studies and Scuola Normale Superiore.
- **Allocation of more than 100.000 Euros**, in one year and half, to help the university community in care activities.
- Institution of **training courses** for the whole university community articulated in modules focused on specific topics such as gender-based violence and harassment; direct and indirect discrimination; stereotypes and language respectful of gender representation.

e) Challenges

For our university, there are two main challenges:

1. The institution of an **after-school facility** that can accommodate university employees' children from 0 to 14 years old;
2. Institutionalisation of a **teaching course, in the local schools**, focused on fundamental concepts such as sex/gender; equality/diversity, gender identity; discrimination, also from a multidisciplinary approach.

f) Recommendations on measures to be taken

The principal recommendations concern the detailed definition of the macro and micro processes, which structure the model at the basis of the activity organisation for Gender Equality and inclusivity.

The University of Pisa is working, through CUG and EDO, to articulate this model, which consists in a clear identification of: functions related to the activities depending on objectives and, to achieve them, it is necessary to identify programmes and missions.

As it is reported in the Gender Equality Plan 2022-2024, every measure specified is instrumental for achieving different goals. The Gender Equality Plan is not a simply bureaucratic fulfilment. In order to make it an efficient procedure, we believe that it is very important to identify the structure of the model that defines the system of relations between the internal and external stakeholders clarifying different roles and functions and the relations between them. Only through a clear definition and organisation of flows, it would be possible to foster the structural change which is the essential goal of the Gender Equality-oriented plan.

3. Contact Point

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Francesca Pecori, Equity and Diversity Office (EDO) - francesca.pecori@unipi.it

4. References

<https://eige.europa.eu/gender-mainstreaming/toolkits/gear/what-gender-equality-plan-gep#:~:text=a%20set%20of%20commitments%20and,a%20process%20of%20structural%20change.>

<https://www.weforum.org/reports/global-gender-gap-report-2023>

<https://op.europa.eu/it/publication-detail/-/publication/67d5a207-4da1-11ec-91ac-01aa75ed71a1>

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0152>

<https://www.unipi.it/index.php/politiche-di-genere>

<https://cug.unipi.it/>

<https://www.unipi.it/index.php/formazione/item/24387-piano-integrato-di-attivita-e-organizzazione>

C. Case study 3: EC2U Alliance

Gender@UC EEA Grants, University of Coimbra

1. Summary

Gender@UC EEA Grants intends to promote Gender Equality in scientific research, either in terms of process management and research career, removing barriers and encouraging balanced participation of male and female researchers in teams, resource management, and decision making, or fostering more inclusive, representative and socially relevant knowledge. By encouraging gender mainstreaming in teams, processes and content of scientific research at the University of Coimbra, Gender@UC EEA Grants will increase the quality and usefulness of the final scientific results and their impact on society.

2. Description

Diversity in scientific research teams, inclusive recruitment processes, inclusive training and communication, and gender-sensitive knowledge production ensure higher quality research with greater impact.

Research is affected by specific social and cultural contexts that shape the way scientists think and see the world. Gender is an implicit part of these contexts. The way scientific knowledge is produced and translated into society is therefore not unrelated to the structural system that produces gender inequalities and allocates distinct hierarchical roles and positions. The invisibility of gender and the (re) production of stereotypes in scientific research not only limits the impacts of research (which may be irrelevant for half the population) but also carries risks and potentiates damages by making recommendations and contributing to changes that have not been inclusively tested.

a) Objectives

The Gender@UC project approach unfolds with the following four objectives:

- i) to combat vertical/horizontal segregation in the research career of women through mentoring and research career support;
- ii) mitigate organisational barriers to access career progression of women in R&D Units through diagnostic actions, support/empowerment of key stakeholders and adaptation of institutional procedures;
- iii) develop inclusive research practices, promoting excellence in scientific research through training actions, revision of templates and monitoring practices of female researchers; and
- iv) promote inclusive communication in research processes.

b) Implementation

The project's work plan comprises 15 activities, 14 aiming at the academic and working community of the UC's R&D Units. These activities are workshops and resources (e.g., guidelines and handbooks) on Gender Equality themes focused on the academic background, such as mainstreaming gender in the research and teaching contents and gender-sensitive language and communication.

c) Successes

Raising awareness of these topics among the academic community, especially female researchers and teachers;

The adherence of the target-public to the different activities of the project exceeded expectations, as all activities were completely booked;

We highlight as a success the fact that we promote and disseminate examples of Women in top and decision-making positions in the Academy;

More than 500 people have already participated in the project activities dedicated to the academic community, but also to the general public.

d) Challenges

The biggest challenge is to increase male participation in the different activities, since they are for everyone. There is still a false idea that this kind of project and the issues related to Gender Equality are only for women.

Another difficulty is to evaluate the actual impact of the project activities on the working lives of all the people who participated in them.

e) Recommendations on measures to be taken

Promote specific actions for men, creating a "safer space" for the sharing of ideas and good practices and to make it possible to alert this group to the importance of Gender Equality, fighting the false idea that this is a subject that concerns only the female gender.

3. Contact Point

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4. References

Project Website: <https://www.uc.pt/en/iii/gender/>

Other references:

- Gender@UC, the initiative | <https://www.uc.pt/en/research/gender-uc/>

- Plan for Equality, Equity and Diversity 2019 – 2023 | <https://www.uc.pt/en/sustainability/equality/index>
- 202 UC Sustainability Report | <https://www.uc.pt/en/sustainability/sustreport/>
- Objectives of the Strategic Plan of the University of Coimbra according to Goal 5 (Gender Equality) of the UN's list of Sustainable Development Goals | <https://www.uc.pt/en/sustainability/goals/index/>

D. Case study 4: EELISA Alliance

Gender Equality Plan and the Gender & Diversity Work Group

1. Summary

EELISA is rooted on the “shared values of democracy, diversity, inclusion and Gender Equality as the *conditio sine qua non* to create a European society based on cooperation and sustainability” ([Statement on Gender Equality](#)). EELISA created the “**EELISA Gender and Equality Working Group**” in November 2021, a group of experts made of representatives from the Gender Equality units and the diversity units of each EELISA partner. The group and the dynamics created within it are considered a major achievement of the Alliance. As part of the work performed by the group, EELISA would like to highlight its **Gender Equality Plan, particularly the annex collecting sex-disaggregated data in research and innovation**, following the example and using similar indicators of the ‘She figures’ report.

2. Description

a) Context

The “**EELISA Gender and Equality Working Group**” ([Gender Equality](#) under EELISA) is a group of experts on Gender Equality and diversity from each EELISA partner. The group is led by EELISA InnoCORE WP1 and EELISA WP7, and has the support of renowned experts in the field such as Inés Sánchez de Madariaga, Assistant Professor of Urban and Regional Planning at the School of Architecture of UPM and Chair of AGGI (Advisory Group on Gender Issues) and Director of the UNESCO Chair on Gender, and Maria Rentetzi, Professor for Science, Technology, and Gender Studies (chair) at Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg (FAU).

The group has been in charge of implementing a whole array of activities to “ensure the mainstreaming of gender dimension in R&I long-term strategies”, including: the EELISA Gender Equality Plan (GEP); the Statement on Gender Equality (signed by Rectors); and the organisation of awareness raising and competence development activities, as planned in EELISA’s GEP.

One key document and a milestone for EELISA R&I branch (InnoCORE) has been the production of the **Gender Equality Plan, particularly the annex collecting sex-disaggregated R&I data**.

b) Objectives

The **EELISA Gender and Equality Working Group** was created to achieve two main objectives:

- To implement the actions foreseen in the respective GA (Grant Agreements) and guarantee coordination between the two projects, exploiting synergies and avoiding overlapping activities.
- To create a network of experts and practitioners sharing experience and best practices, and in connection with this, to create a sense of belonging to EELISA.

The **Gender Equality Plan** —done under EELISA InnoCORE— had as objectives:

- To perform an assessment of the Gender Equality state-of-play in our HEIs, covering two elements: collection of sex-disaggregated data in R&I and analyses of gender policies in place.
- To agree and implement actions at consortium-level based on the analyses above.

c) *Implementation*

EELISA's GEP follows the methods, tools and structures proposed by [EIGE](#) (European Institute for Gender Equality), therefore using the [GEAR tool](#) (Gender Equality in Academia and Research). In November 2021, a first version of the GEP was produced. To be able to compare their situation accurately, partners agreed on a common set of sex-disaggregated indicators, collected the agreed data during the Summer 2022 and produced an annex updating the GEP in November 2022. **The annex provides a picture of the situation at EELISA partners regarding gender balance in R&I: doctoral studies, academic and research staff, research and innovation output.**

Key take-aways: Gender in R&I at EELISA level

With over 15,000 students enrolled in doctoral programmes in the academic year 2021/2022 at EELISA level, [women represented 40% of doctoral students](#). With regards to the proportion of women among doctoral graduates —number of students having completed and successfully defended their PhD thesis—, in the year 2020-2021, an average of 37% were women.

Academic and research workforce at EELISA amounts to aprox. 9,540 people, out of which 6,384 (67%) are men and 3,156 (33%) are women. [Gender gaps and gender balance vary significantly from one EELISA partner to another](#), ITU being in general terms the partner with the smallest gender gap followed by UPB and PSL.

[The share of women among academic staff at EELISA-level declines as we advance to higher positions in the academic career](#). In 2021 women represented 29% of EELISA Grade A academicians (highest rank at which research is performed, usually professorships), ranging from 39% at ITU, 35% at PSL and 31% at UPB to 5.7% at BME, 9.6% at SNS, 12% at ENPC, 16.2% at UPM and 17% at FAU. At the European level, the proportion of women declines from 46.6% in grade C positions to 26.2% in grade A in 2018 ('She figures').

At the EELISA-level, women occupy 32% of decision-making positions. Considering the baseline share (33%), this suggests that women are reaching top-level positions.

Additionally, EELISA runs a survey among its researchers in order to get qualitative feedback. It is important to highlight that out of the ~193 written answers to the open questions, over 40 respondents mentioned maternity, childcare and an uneven distribution of family duties as main obstacles hindering the career progress of women researchers.

As foreseen in the GEP, EELISA has organised a set of [consortium-level activities for the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in R&I](#):

- I EELISA round-table '[Women who make science happen](#)', for the 11th February 2022 (International day of Girls and Women in Science).
- II EELISA round-table '[Parenting in the XXIst Century: raising children, giving up science?](#)', for the 11th February 2023 (the topic was chosen based on the results of the qualitative survey).
- EELISA workshop '[Gender Dimension in Research](#)' (5th October 2022).

d) Successes, Challenges and Recommendations on measures to be taken

All EELISA partners are not only developing institutional policies and measures, but in all our HEIs we find researchers, administrative staff, students, academics involved on a personal basis in supporting Gender Equality; Whenever activities are organised, we find a genuine interest and commitment.

Creating a sense of belonging to something bigger than your own institution (i.e. to EELISA Alliance) takes time; The renewal of Alliances will be key for keeping the momentum and consolidate successes.

Keeping the momentum is complicated; Activities (very particularly the round-tables, which had an active involvement of many people from all our partners) were extremely useful for creating a truly EELISA-wide network of practitioners and creating a sense of ownerships and a sense of belonging to something bigger than your own institution (i.e., to the EELISA Alliance). However, keeping the momentum is difficult and it depends very much on facilitation and coordination.

The Gender Equality Plan focused on research and innovation indicators. It is recommended extending the data gathered to other categories of staff and students (bachelor's and master's students, administrative staff, even alumni) and also analyse the situation regarding entrepreneurship. The fact that the analyses only considered research and innovation is due to the separation of education and R&I.

The collection of the agreed sex-disaggregated data proved to be a more complex exercise than planned and some initially agreed KPIs had to be disregarded. For the production of the annex, EELISA kept those KPIs for which a minimum of five partners could provide data.

Further analysis is needed about reasons: Why some partners are performing better than others? Why women are less represented as innovators? Why women are less present among Grade A staff (is it only a question of age)?

3. Contact Point

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4. References

<https://eelisa.eu/gender-equality-and-diversity/>

<https://eelisa.eu/events/women-who-make-science-happen-an-eelisa-roundtable/>

<https://eelisa.eu/events/workshop-on-gender-dimension-research/>

<https://eelisa.eu/events/raising-children-giving-up-science-sign-up-for-the-ii-eelisa-roundtable-on-parenting-and-stem-in-the-21st-century/>

<https://eelisa.eu/an-alliance-committed-to-close-gender-gaps-in-higher-education/>

https://eelisa.eu/revisit_idwgs_2023/

<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/knowledge-publications-tools-and-data/interactive-reports/she-figures-2021>

Workshop on 'Gender Dimension in Research'

SAVE THE DATE
5 October, 2022

10:00 h | 12:30 h CET

European University

More info: www.eelisa.eu

Horizon2020
European Union Funding
for Research & Innovation

E. Case study 5: ENHANCE Alliance

1. Summary

The ENHANCE Alliance encompasses ten major research-intensive universities focusing on science and technology, laying the foundations for an innovative European University of Technology. The ENHANCE Alliance aims to empower students, researchers and society to address the challenges of tomorrow responsibly, challenges set out in the Green Deal and Digital Transformation.

Diversity, inclusivity and Gender Equality lead to more innovative and sustainable communities. We want to **mainstream** inclusion, diversity, and equality (IDE) at all levels in our Alliance. We want to **empower** groups that are facing barriers. We want to **train** our community about IDE issues. We consider and promote these core values in all our activities. Visit <https://enhanceuniversity.eu/diversity/> to discover more.

2. Description

a) Context

ENHANCE regularly offers short-term learning offers and public events for students and staff. Through our Alliance we provide several resources and useful tools like the support pack for sustainable entrepreneurship and innovation, guidelines for bias-awareness selection, a useful glossary, ENHANCE annual diversity reports and more. You can also find out more about the diversity management of each ENHANCE university. ENHANCE has also developed a mobility tool where students and staff can explore different types of services and infrastructures related to an exchange semester, research mobility placement, or any other kind of mobility opportunity – enabling mobility for all.

Visit <https://enhanceuniversity.eu/diversity/> to discover more.

b) Objectives

Overall objectives:

- mainstream inclusion, diversity, and equality (IDE) at all levels in our Alliance
- empower groups that are facing barriers
- train our community on IDE issues

c) Implementation

Following the objectives of DEI in the ENHANCE Alliance, the activities focus on:

1. Learning offers and public events incl. awareness raising (e.g., Anti-bias lunchbreaks, pre-departure trainings, summer schools on Diversity, MOOC)
2. Resources and tools (ENHANCE Guidelines Bias-aware selection)
3. Mobility for All (Comparison Page & “Welcome sentences”)

4. Data collection and Monitoring (Annual Diversity Report)
5. Networking and Knowledge Sharing
 - 5.1. D&I Network within ENHANCE
 - 6.1. D&I Hub between Alliances
 - 6.2. Networking with associated partners
6. Outreach and empowerment (STEM Girls Competition, ENHANCE LGBTQ+ networking, African Students in ENHANCE)
7. Community Building (Newsletter 500+ recipients)
8. Impact orientation outside of the Alliance as well (13% external participation in our events so far)
9. Gender balance in selection and recruitment processes

d) *Successes*

See the [annual diversity reports](#) from 2021 and 2022. The 2023 report will be published in October 2023.

e) *Challenges*

Through the work on DEI in the ENHANCE Alliance, three identified challenges are:

1. Data protection regulations for monitoring DEI aspects (It is not impossible but it makes data collection more difficult. We need data to monitor and improve the situation.)
2. Complex and diverse situations in all countries (A proper mapping is needed. A flexible approach is necessary that embraces this diversity in regulations, legislation and differences. There is no one size fits all solution. It takes a longer time to understand this diversity but it is doable.)
3. Communication on the local level of each university (It is not easy to find the right platform, local networks to address, to involve, to encourage and engage.)

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

1. When we work on addressing “underrepresented groups”, involve them. Don’t talk about them. Talk WITH them.
2. Involve also the majority of the community (the privileged ones, the ones with opportunities, the ones who are not underrepresented. We need them as allies).
3. Encourage bottom-up involvement (People should come to you with their ideas to change things on local levels).

3. Contact Point

Work Package Lead and Ombudsman for Diversity: Melih.oezkardes@enhanceuniversity.eu

4. References

<https://enhanceuniversity.eu/diversity/>

F. Case study 6: ENLIGHT Alliance

Akademe Programme, academic leadership project (University of the Basque Country)

1. Summary

Akademe programme is a training and support programme for female teachers and researchers to acquire self-leadership and leadership skills, in order to access and remain in positions of responsibility in research, teaching and knowledge transfer in the academic career.

The starting point of the programme was the challenge set out in the article 5.3 of the UPV/EHU [III Gender Equality Plan \(2019-2022\), which sets out a series of commitments intended to generalise an integrated gender approach throughout university activity \(training, research, relationship with society, people and governance and resources\)](#). According to this article, it is a challenge of the UPV/EHU “To promote the increase in the number of women in leadership positions and the highest responsibility of the university (female full professors, female main researchers in projects and high-level academic positions”).

2. Description

a) Context

According to the 2018 Equal Figures Report published by the Equality Direction annually, the main female researchers and female thesis directors did not reach 40% parity. Percentage of female full professors was 25%, with little presence in areas of knowledge of masculinised fields, particularly in engineering and informatics. There was also a low participation of female professors and researchers in decision-making and managerial responsibility positions, such as female deans (31.58%) and department female directors (38.74%). This situation generated inequality in the internal distribution of academic roles.

The knowledge of these data led the UPV/EHU, as a Basque public university, to assume its responsibility in achieving the goal of real equality between women and men in the university. Moreover, it was necessary to implement policies and actions in order to break the glass ceilings and redirecting the cultural, relational and power factors that block the access of the female academics to the responsibility. Thus, it was a response to the 5th SDG of the United Nations Agenda 2030 and the European Commission's strategy (2016/2019-2020/2025) to integrate public and private decision-making power in the Common European Space.

b) Objectives

The specific context that integrates the academic and university career of female teachers and researchers makes Akademe a functional and relevant tool to facilitate the leadership of women in their academic career. It is based on three pillars: “to lead myself; to lead other people and, above all, to build support networks for collective empowerment.”

This objective integrates specific ones such as:

- Create a space of trust and security that allows the activation of a collective empowerment process for women.
- Train females in skills and techniques to improve their leadership capacity to build with other people and lead groups and teams.
- To promote the participation of females in the network to share experiences, successes and difficulties, as well as to establish pacts and supportive relationships to access and maintain positions of responsibility.
- Identify the particular and common needs, in order to give continuity to the programme.

c) *Implementation*

The Akademe programme is led by an external coach. Its implementation requires 40 hours of classroom and 10 hours on-line, which are structured in 8 sessions, 2 of them are plenaries (at the beginning and at the end of the programme). Each session lasts for 5 hours and the frequency of the sessions is approximately 15 days, so the programme lasts for 4 months.

The groups have of a maximum of 15 people, with an average of 30 people per year, and they are distributed on two of the campuses of the university.

Among the periodic sessions, the participants are given tasks consisting in the implementation of the work of the face-to-face sessions, shared reflections, as well as brief readings on themes and questions developed in the classroom. In total, there are 4 tasks to be deliverables.

At the end of the programme, in the last plenary session, a collective evaluation is made in order to express positive aspects and new proposals for improvement.

There is also a computer support (eGelapi platform) managed by an expert teacher in digital educational management, so that a common virtual space is available to share applied learning, to strengthen knowledge and to promote links between participants by creating an effective communication forum during the programme to resolve questions for methodological purposes.

d) *Successes*

Since 2018, 6 editions have been held, one per academic year. In total, 200 women have participated.

Once the training has been completed, female participants will acquire these skills:

- Identify their potential to build their own leadership style.
- Manage their fears and limiting beliefs.
- Improve their skills for effective communication.
- Build conscious and intentional female relationships at work with a shared purpose.
- Have a common language that facilitates the co-creation of shared strategies.
- Establish supportive relationships among female academics to advance equal opportunities in the University of the Basque Country.

The annual report on “Equality in Figures”⁷, prepared by the Direction for Equality, shows that the University of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU) is progressing favorably in relation to gender indicators in leadership and in access to positions of responsibility and decision-making.

Based on the data contained in the 2022 report:

- Percentage of female head researchers has increased to 43.90 %
- Percentage of female thesis directors has reached 42.36 %
- The Rector's Team is led by a woman and the team is composed by 7 female vice-presidents, one female manager and 7 male vice-presidents.
- Number of female deans reached 42.11%
- Number of department female directors reached 32.43%.

e) Challenges

The Akademe programme is a fundamentally leadership programme, which can be applied in diverse context of organisations and institutions.

UPV/EHU has been able to detect one of the weaknesses in the academic career of women and has addressed it using the most efficient tool to overcome the challenge, which is training female academics through learning the skills and competences needed to lead themselves and lead others in a very specific institutional framework.

Likewise, they acquire competencies that help to establish goals and develop projects. These competencies help, on the other hand, to build a support network that strengthens participants and provides them with a stronger perception of their abilities.

f) Recommendations on measures to be taken

Based on the data provided, the support of the different activities performed by women who have participated in the Akademe programme (2018-2022), endorses the impact that this programme has had on the leadership of the academics of the University of the Basque Country.

In particular, the acquisition of these competencies makes it easier for academics to gain security and agree to lead research projects and groups, as well as to assume addresses of thesis works.

These two activities are fundamental for the women to get merits required in the accreditation of access to the different levels of academic hierarchy granted by quality agencies (Unibasq, Aneca), as well as to achieve sufficient projection between the national and international scientific community.

This improvement in the female careers helps to reduce the salary gap.

⁷ Available at <https://www.ehu.eus/documents/2007376/43960833/EHU-Equality-in-figures-2022.pdf/20a4c613-ba40-c8d0-7d72-3183e7f9f9d3?t=1683201166714>

3. Contact Point

Direction for Equality (University of the Basque Country): berdintasuna@ehu.eus

4. References

<https://www.ehu.eus/documents/2007376/43960833/Akademe-Programme.pdf/68350666-2ca9-f33b-a462-efec3f811bf7?t=1682077383075>

<https://www.ehu.eus/documents/2007376/43960833/EHU-Equality-in-figures-2022.pdf/20a4c613-ba40-c8d0-7d72-3183e7f9f9d3?t=1683201166714>

Figure 1. Akademe Programme (University of the Basque Country – ENLIGHT Alliance)

G. Case study 7: European Reform University Alliance (ERUA)

1. Summary

Re:ERUA, the research component of the European Reform University Alliance (ERUA), aims to develop an engagement strategy and critically explore societal engagement through the lens of Responsible Research and Innovation. ERUA emphasises the promotion of diversity, gender balance, equal opportunities and inclusivity in academia as a key element of the Alliance to mitigate the different national legislative frameworks and starting points of universities. The Alliance's engagement on this issue will include a gender and sex dimension in its engagement strategy: mapping best practices, mainstreaming gender in strategic documents, and implementing a joint Gender Equality plan with pillars of inclusion, protection and awareness-raising campaigns. Re:ERUA also plans to organise training programmes and research seminars on the gender dimension and to promote inclusivity through cooperation with social actors. A dedicated website will serve as a repository of resources.

2. Description

a) Context

The European Reform University Alliance (ERUA) was launched in 2020, with its research component, Re:ERUA, initiated in November 2021. ERUA's members share a commitment to an experimental approach, emphasising the importance of people and the value of diversity as a resource for innovation.

While some partner universities have made significant progress in fostering gender balance, equal opportunities, and inclusivity in academia, there are variations in the level of advancement among the Alliance's institutions. In terms of academic personnel, the universities generally maintain an equal distribution between genders. However, there is limited available information regarding key management positions across universities or balance between full professors, assistant professors etc. Moreover, despite women's overall success in higher education, they remain strongly underrepresented in certain fields of science, such as STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics).

Addressing these challenges and promoting gender balance, equal opportunities, and inclusivity in academia require collective efforts within the Alliance. By sharing best practices, engaging in dialogue, and collaborating, the ERUA universities can work towards improving representation, dismantling gender biases, and creating a more inclusive research and innovation ecosystem. This aligns with the overarching commitment to diversity as a catalyst for innovation within the ERUA.

b) Objectives

Re:ERUA's activities focusing on the sex and gender dimension are limited, but it is a key and cross-cutting element in building our Alliance. One of the main activities for the gender dimension is to promote specific training initiatives linked with diversity and gender dimension in order to facilitate inclusion and access in R&I (developed in 2024). The gender and sex dimensions will

be included in our engagement strategy for R&I within the Alliance. The gender lens is used as a strategy for creating impact.

c) *Implementation*

- 1. Mapping out best practices and shared initiatives on gender dimension** to identify and document best practices across member universities. This process involves gathering successful gender balance initiatives in R&I and (within) the University community.
- 2. Including Gender Dimension in strategic documents and decision-making bodies** for institutional commitment. This means that gender balance considerations will be explicitly included in the Alliance's mission and strategic deliverables (when relevant).
- 3. Implementation of a joint “Gender Equality Plan”** for the Alliance including common values and with a specific methodology
This plan should comprise three pillars:
 - Inclusion: The question of representativeness from a gender perspective: both in terms of numbers and participation in decision-making processes.
 - Protection: simplified reporting procedures in case of gender based and sexual violence and discrimination.
 - Awareness campaigns / increasing sensitivity: Exchange and mapping of best practices and recommendations for the future.
- 4. Organising joint training programme (deliverable)** and research seminars on gender dimension to foster a deeper understanding of the gender dimension in R&I. These seminars will focus on key topics such as gender and ethics, and responsible research and innovation (RRI) in a care perspective. Our Alliance has indeed a strong expertise in these areas with two research units dedicated to gender and intersectional research at [UP8](#) and [RUC](#), along with a total of 14 research laboratories in the Alliance that work on different topics, including gender.
- 5. Launching a dedicated webpage on ERUA website** that should be focused on gender balance and equal opportunities. This webpage will serve as a resource repository, offering information and tools related to Gender Equality, with a particular focus on R&I.
- 6. Organising a two-day final seminar about Gender innovation (deliverable)** that should be a wrap-up of activities within the Alliance, open the discussion with external stakeholders and presentation of results. It could also be a relevant moment to invite all the Alliances of FOREU2 that participate in this joint deliverable in order to update our recommendations.

d) *Successes*

ERUA does not have a success story at the Alliance level to tell yet, however individual universities within the Alliance have implemented several activities and initiatives to promote gender balance and inclusivity. Among those practices, practice acknowledges and respects individuals' gender

identities e.g student ID card that indicate their preferred name and gender; web pages dedicated to gender-based and sexual violence; partnership with experimented association to support students who may require assistance related to sexual harassment. All universities have a GEP.

e) *Challenges*

One of the limitations and difficulties in implementing measures to enable Gender Equality is rooted in the different national legislative frameworks, which cannot allow a homogenous development of Gender Equality policies in the consortium universities. Pay transparency, parental leave days remain structural vectors of change that affect the gender balance of universities. Universities may face limitations in implementing uniform measures due to these legal differences.

Moreover, each university starts from very different starting points and views on what the gender dimension is; often, the understanding of gender is limited to a binary notion of man vs. woman, which fails to encompass the complexity of gender dimensions in academia. Very different starting points in the consortium universities regarding the awareness, the resources and the actions to be taken to tackle sexist and sexual phenomena as well the development of related policies and inclusion.

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

Considering the growing number of intra-Alliances mobilities of academic staff, students, and PhD candidates it is crucial to prioritise everyone's safety. To address issues related to sexist, sexual, and gender-based violence during mobility periods, we recommend appointing a dedicated contact person in each university of the consortium to support individuals on mobility.

To address discrimination and biases related to gender and sexual orientation in the workplace, we recommend implementing targeted training sessions for universities' management positions within the Alliance. To address the phenomenon of self-censorship within and promote a culture of open expression and diversity of ideas, we recommend implementing training and support programmes specifically designed to tackle self-censorship in academic settings.

We recommend the promotion of transparency. ERUA Universities have willingly agreed to share their scores with the public. Trust and transparency are vital catalysts for driving change.

To further promote Gender Equality and inclusivity within the ERUA Alliance, we recommend initiating a reflection process on the creation of a Gender Index. This index would serve as a comprehensive measurement tool to assess and track the progress of member universities in achieving Gender Equality goals in Research and Innovation.

3. Contact Point

Re:ERUA coordinator - Claire DOUET : claire.douet02@univ-paris8.fr

4. References

European Commission, She Figures - Gender in Research and Innovation Statistics and Indicators, 2021 : <https://op.europa.eu/o/opportal-service/download-handler?identifier=67d5a207-4da1-11ec-91ac-01aa75ed71a1&format=pdf&language=en&productionSystem=cellar&part=>

French Ministry Minister of Higher Education, Research and Innovation, Moving towards Gender Equality? (Key Figures), 2016 https://www.enseignementsup-recherche.gouv.fr/sites/default/files/imported_files/documents/gender_eqlity_key_figures_630898.pdf

What is the gender dimension in research? https://kjonnsforskning.no/sites/default/files/what_is_the_gender_dimension_roggkorsvik_kil_den_genderresearch.no.pdf

The Commission's Gender Equality strategy: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en

H. Case study 8: EUNICE Alliance

REUNICE SwafS Project – Communication activities on Gender Equality

1. Summary

Within the REUNICE SwafS project, we are carrying out several communication and dissemination activities to raise awareness on diversity, inclusiveness and Gender Equality. The most highlighted actions achieved by the Communication Board were the following:

- The preparation of the Diversity, Inclusiveness and Gender Equality Style Manual that establishes some common criteria when approaching communications on the cross-cutting theme of the Reunice Project related to the values of diversity, inclusiveness and Gender Equality.
- The awareness raising action – “International Day of Women and Girls in Science” where the work of female researchers from all EUNICE partner universities is highlighted to support the female role in research, through their own professional experience.

2. Description

a) Context

It has been agreed that communication activities and therefore the use of language has a considerable impact as far as diversity, inclusiveness and Gender Equality is concerned. One of the ideas in the REUNICE Project was to work on a common approach to these issue by preparing a Diversity, Inclusiveness and Gender Equality Style Manual that could serve the whole Alliance while working on communication and dissemination activities. This guide has been developed by the EUNICE Communication Board, that is the body in the Alliance that works on the communication and dissemination activities. The document was developed by the communication staff, which has gained expertise from working in an international environment and from the previous experience of working in communication activities related to the project.

EUNICE’s Style Manual establishes some common criteria and recommendations related to the inclusiveness and Gender Equality values that are highlighted in the project’s proposal and the Communication Strategy in alignment with the Erasmus+ Programme. It serves to focus on diversity in the Alliance, among the individuals who work in the project and those who are the beneficiaries of the project. It also concerns the subject of inclusiveness, to ensure the project benefits a global society based on European values and is free of discrimination from a communication point of view.

The decision to celebrate the “International Day of Women and Girls in Science” in the Alliance to provide examples to follow and encourage females to engage into any area of science, without feeling limited by their gender. This awareness-raising activity intended to showcase some examples of remarkable female researchers of our partner universities and their work within the Alliance. It was done through a social media campaign featuring these researchers of diverse ages in their daily work. Real examples and real people are more likely to reach the public consciousness and, at the same time, the social recognition is also better.

Task 4.5 of the REUNICE project consists of developing in the entire universities' communities' personal dispositions such as openness, sensitivity to individual and community particularities - in short, attentiveness to others through concrete life experiences of students and staff.

To pilot, assist and supervise the activities developed in this task, a working group has been set, as this is a cross-cutting approach. Its objectives are to feed up and monitor the observation and analysis process and to contribute to the implementation of pilot actions and courses.

b) Objectives

- To raise social awareness against discrimination issues and remove obstacles for recruitment and scientific career development, seeing diversity as a richness.
- To encourage gender-consciousness at the decision-making, learning and research levels.
- To reduce the discriminating, especially sexist, language at the universities.
- To contribute to eliminate the inequalities in all fields of research as a way to promote creative talents, reach excellence and enhance innovation.
- To promote gender balance.
- To make women working in science and research more visible.
- To encourage girls to choose scientific areas of study of their election.
- To develop a more accessible, open and welcoming environment for the diversity of profiles in our universities, in particular for all genders.

c) Implementation

The Alliance Communication Board worked on and issued the Diversity, Inclusiveness and Gender Equality Style Manual with a special focus and importance to be given to the use of an inclusive language and other communication elements such as images and accessibility guidelines. In the Alliance, special attention is given while addressing the university community and students as they are the ones who will pass what they learn to the next generations. Communication activities, websites, forms are highly effective places to promote the use of inclusive languages.

The manual was disseminated internally among the staff of the REUNICE Project and, as part of the exploitation actions, delivered to the departments/units dedicated to inclusion and equality affairs within the partner universities.

As far as research is concerned, women can be invisible if they are not explicitly named, this is why the "International Day of Women and Girls in Science" in the Alliance was celebrated with photos of our female colleagues from the partner universities.

At the moment, the partners involved in the inclusiveness working group are discovering measures in place in other universities and exchanging best practices in order to help their communities become more inclusive within the university.

We have discovered that, in addition to most universities having gender plans that include the entire university community, several others have awareness-raising campaigns and specific

actions around the International Day for the Elimination of Violence against Women. Furthermore, some universities have special events, such as BTU's annual CSD action weeks for Cottbus and the Niederlausitz region, Diversity Day, the Queer Stammtisch, the prize for the best female MINT student, special support for scientists, and so on.

In September, the work of this group will focus on implementing actions and pilot courses to develop more training and initiatives to promote diversity and inclusiveness in EUNICE universities.

d) *Successes*

Good reception of the Style Manual and interest of the university community in the International Day of Women and Girls in Science.

e) *Challenges*

While working on the Style Manual in English, we had to take into account most of the staff involved in the process (both the people working on the manual and the final recipients) and the Alliance members that are not native English-speaking persons.

Furthermore, this Style manual, only available in English, does not answer the need for style manuals in local languages, which are often more gender-oriented than the English language.

Additionally, in some institutions these matters are not managed from a central department in charge of them but from separate units.

Finally, when designing these activities, we could not completely account for people who don't identify as male or female, for example when choosing a pre-existing initiative as "International Day of Women and Girls in Science".

The way in which the public with fewer opportunities are identified, supported and actions designed is very much linked to the cultural context. It is therefore necessary to go through a long phase of discovery and analysis of each other's practices before being able to start working together.

Furthermore, the working group on Inclusiveness has not chosen to limit itself to one type of lacks opportunity in particular, such as such as gender-based discrimination, precisely so that each partner can bring in practices that they have developed and not focus on any weaknesses identified within the consortium. However, working on a broader subject adds a layer of complexity.

3. Contact Point

Marta Malepszak – marta.malepszak@put.poznan.pl ; eunice@put.poznan.pl

4. References

<https://eunice-university.eu/research/>

<https://eunice-university.eu/research/wp-content/uploads/sites/2/2022/09/D-6.3.-REUNICE-Diversity-Inclusiveness-and-Gender-Equality-Style-Manual-FINAL.pdf>

<https://eunice-university.eu/11f-womenandgirlsinscience/>

<https://eunice-university.eu/international-day-of-women-and-girls-in-science/>

<https://eunice-university.eu/access-for-all-in-higher-education/>

I. Case study 9: EURECA-PRO Alliance 1

Montanuniversität Leoben (MUL), RE-EURECA-PRO

1. Summary

The Montanuniversität Leoben is committed to the implementation of equal opportunities by people of all gender identities, ethnicities, religions, beliefs, age groups or sexual orientations. Action is taken against any kind of discrimination, harassment and bullying. MUL has adopted an *Action Plan for the Promotion of Women* (2005), an *Equality Plan* (2017), and a *Diversity Strategy* (2019).

MUL is committed to a lived culture of diversity, Gender Equality, appreciation, respect and tolerance for the groups that are underrepresented in society. The university is committed to interacting with all stakeholders in society and acts as a role model with regard to the implementation of all aspects of diversity and Gender Equality.

2. Description

a) Context

The Montanuniversität is fully aware of its social responsibility and demonstrates competence in gender mainstreaming and diversity management. It has implemented various action plans, strategies, programmes and structural changes that support the diversity ethos and establish Gender Equality in the higher education environment.

b) Objectives

Considerations of diversity, parity and equal opportunities are a central dimension of the university's ethos and embedded in its structures and activities. The main objective of the university with regards to equality and diversity is to promote a cooperative working atmosphere that is free of prejudices against all people, regardless of gender, age, origin, nationality, sexual orientation, religion and world view.

c) Implementation

In 2007, an *Action Plan for the Promotion of Women* was implemented, followed by an *Equality Plan* In 2017 and a *Diversity Strategy* in 2019. The goal of the *Action Plan for the Promotion of Women* is to combat the under-representation of women in academia, and the goal of the *Equality Plan* is to guarantee equal opportunities for all university members and applicants to the university. The *Diversity Strategy* is anchored at the management level as well as in teaching and research.

In addition, a *Working Group for Equal Opportunities* (AKG) has been established, which is involved in all HR processes at the University, from job advertisements to job interviews. The Working Group is committed to the implementation of equal opportunities and the compatibility of work/study and family.

The University has also established a dedicated *Equality Coordination Office* for tasks related to equality, the advancement of women, and gender research.

d) *Successes*

The activities and support offered by the *Working Group for Equal Opportunities* (AKG) has had a major impact on the university's culture of diversity. The AKG carries out gender monitoring to check the proportion of women in university collegial bodies and committees. It has the right to object to incorrect compositions of collegial bodies and the right to appeal to the arbitration commission.

The *Equality Coordination Office* for tasks related to diversity organises regular activities and hosts events such as EU Diversity Month, International Women's Day events and diversity skills training courses. It offers counseling in case of discrimination and bullying, advice on aspects of diversity in teaching, and advice on including diversity in research.

e) *Challenges*

Gender discrimination in higher education and research is an ongoing problem at university level. Rigorous monitoring and the implementation of adequate measures and processes are needed to achieve Gender Equality and create inclusive working environments.

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

A conscious focus on gender mainstreaming is needed when planning interdisciplinary research agendas across the university. For example, attention must be paid to gender-sensitive language and gender-specific data collection and analysis in research papers and activities.

The utilisation of research sources and services must become more transparent and women and men should be equally involved in decision making processes.

Equal pay between the sexes (gender pay parity) must be guaranteed and regular gender audits should be carried out.

Helpful for the realisation of Gender Equality and the creation of inclusive academic environments are gender action plans, gender working groups at student and staff level, gender awareness raising activities as well as gender-sensitive approaches to mentoring and health promotion in the workplace.

3. *Contact Point*

Koordinationsstelle für Gleichstellung und Diversität (Coordination Office for Equality and Diversity): diversitaet@unileoben.ac.at

Arbeitskreis für Gleichbehandlungsfragen (Working Group for Equal Opportunities): akg@unileoben.ac.at

4. References

<https://diversitaet.unileoben.ac.at/>

J. Case study 10: EURECA-PRO Alliance 2

University of Petroșani, RE-EURECA-PRO

1. Summary

A fundamental value of the University of Petroșani (UP) is equality, both between women and men, which aims to ensure that all members of the academic community, regardless of sex and gender identity, have the same opportunities, rights, and obligations. UP ensures equal opportunities for both women and men in learning, teaching, research, administration, and management; it ensures equal working conditions, non-discriminatory access to education and teaching, courses, and study programmes at all levels, regardless of gender, with respect for religious specificity. UP actively promotes the equal rights of employees and students and seeks to prevent gender discrimination and discourage tendencies of sexual and moral harassment, both within the academic community and in the social sphere. Another direction in which UP is engaged is the fight against gender stereotypes, understood as organised systems of consensual beliefs and opinions, perceptions, and prejudices in relation to gender.

2. Description

a) Context

The University of Petroșani (UP) leads work package 6 “Inclusiveness of Scientific Communities” in RE-EURECA-PRO Horizon 2020 project. This is an example of the impact of the Alliance on individual partners, as UP was the only university without a systemic strategy to prevent gender discrimination. After a careful analysis of the Gender Equality plans and strategies of the other partner universities in RE-EURECA-PRO, as a result in March 2023 UP has adopted a “Strategy to combat and prevent gender discrimination” approved by the university senate.

The strategy is the official document of the University of Petroșani, which defines the coordination of the policy to promote Gender Equality, being developed in accordance with national and European legislation relevant to the field.

b) Objectives

Within the University of Petroșani, to implement the Strategy to combat and prevent gender discrimination, a plan for the promotion of Gender Equality is implemented through a series of actions on the following main components:

- a) assuming the responsibility of management structures for the elimination of all forms of discrimination against women and the promotion of Gender Equality.
- b) ensuring equal conditions of study, work, and career advancement.
- c) stimulating and supporting Gender Equality in terms of competitiveness and excellence.
- d) fostering an inclusive and gender-sensitive organisational climate.

e) preventing harassment and gender discrimination.

c) *Implementation*

Considering that the strategy was adopted only 3 months ago, we cannot say that many actions have been implemented. UP is in the phase of disseminating the strategy to departments.

d) *Successes*

Adoption of the strategy and its compliance with national and European legislation.

e) *Challenges*

In the context where, in general, political correctness is a rather misunderstood and misapplied concept, the University of Petrosani is an institutional-organisational complex, which is part of the Romanian education system, being semi-centralised. Thus, the axiological system that governs the current activity of this academic institution is based on the following fundamental values: professional competence, scientific and teaching performance, and moral probity. However, there is a need for greater awareness of the problem and specific initiatives to achieve it.

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

The main recommendation is to continue working on improving the actions that are being taken within the university while consolidating the strategy.

3. Contact Point

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4. References

<https://www.upet.ro/documente/2023/Strategia%20de%20combatere%20si%20prevenire%20a%20discriminarii%20de%20gen%20UPET.pdf>

K. Case study 11: EURECA-PRO Alliance 3

Technical University of Crete, RE-EURECA-PRO

1. Summary

The Gender Equality Plan (GAP) of the Technical University of Crete, was formulated according to the specifications of Horizon Europe and the new Framework for Research and Innovation (2021-2027) of the Council of Europe. It sets as a prerequisite the guarantee of Gender Equality throughout the community of the institution. With a priority commitment to Gender Equality, the existence of a Gender Equality Action Plan is henceforth a criterion for gender mainstreaming in the content of teaching, research and innovation, in administrative and management structures, and in the processes, administration and the student community, and aims to promote Gender Equality in the gender balance and protection in all the above-mentioned collaborating institutions.

2. Description

a) Context and Objectives

The Gender Equality Committee (GEC) of the Technical University of Crete has the following responsibilities:

- (a) to draw up action plans to promote and ensure substantive equality in the field of education and training at the institution and to prepare an annual report, which shall be submitted to the Senate,
- (b) to recommend to the competent bodies measures to promote equality and to ensure that equality is promoted and guaranteed,
- (c) to provide information and training to members of the academic community on issues relating to Gender Equality and the promotion of Gender Equality and to inform and educate the academic community on gender and equality issues,
- (d) to provide mediation services in cases of complaints of discrimination or harassment,
- (e) to promote the development of MSc programmes and the organisation of seminars and lectures focusing on gender studies,
- (f) to promote the preparation of studies and research on issues related to gender,
- (g) to assist victims of discrimination when they complain of discrimination,
- (h) to contribute to the development of a more favorable framework for the harmonisation of family life and professional life of men and women within the institution,
- (i) to contribute to reducing the phenomenon of the 'glass ceiling' and the obstacles that female faculty members might face in their professional development.

b) *Implementation*

Methodological Framework

The proposed actions of the GEC of the Technical University of Crete will focus on taking positive measures and actions as described in detail in the Action Plan for Gender Equality - male, female and non-binary, (Gender Equality Plan/GEP (hereinafter referred to as GEP), taking into account specific needs and challenges as they emerge from the gender map of the university.

The procedure adopted by the Gender Equality Committee of the Technical University of Crete to develop the annual policy of the Gender Equality Policy is based on the logic of a cyclical evaluation scheme, as recommended by the Horizon Europe Guidance on Gender Equality Plans.

- A. Annual mapping of the gender map and identification of emerging needs within the institution,
- B. Addressing challenges and designing a strategy and specific objectives (planning).
- C. Implementation of actions at horizontal and vertical level, setting of milestones, allocation of activities.
- D. Monitoring of action plans and feedback.
- E. Evaluation of results and reporting.
- F. Review, redesign, and decision-making.

c) *Challenges*

It is observed that the gender distribution differs between the different categories of Staff: The members of the academic staff are predominantly male. 83.5 % of faculty members are men compared to 16.5 % of women, and in the other categories of the academic staff 61,7 % are men and 38,3 % women, while the administrative staff are predominantly female (66.1% of women compared to 33.9% of men).

Unfortunately, in the Technical University of Crete, the prevalence of the stereotype that women are for administrative tasks, while men are for educational, technical and research tasks is confirmed.

It is therefore important for the GEC to set as objective actions for combating gender bias and stereotypes.

A very positive initiative – related to the Gender Equality Action Plan 2022-2025 - has already been taken by the students at the Technical University of Crete, as they have already created a Gender Equality Group.

d) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

In the proposed draft of the Gender Equality Plan, no data have been collected on the positions of responsibility of employees of the Technical University of Crete, so one of the future actions of the GEC will be to collect data on positions of responsibility.

3. Contact Point

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4. References

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L. Case study 12: EURECA-PRO Alliance 4

Silesian University of Technology, RE-EURECA-PRO

1. Summary

The Silesian University of Technology has introduced in 2022 the Gender Equality Plan. For the purpose of the plan development, a dedicated team was created at SUT, chaired by Vice Rector for Science and Development. The process of Plan development included quantitative analysis by gender based on statistical data and conducting an anonymous qualitative survey of personal experiences and perceptions of the problem of Gender Equality. After data analysis, goals and activities to be developed and implemented in a sustainable manner throughout the duration of the Plan were formulated. Plan for the utilisation of existing and acquiring new resources for implementation purposes was also developed and indicators to monitor the implementation of the Plan and its development in the future were elaborated.

2. Description

a) Context

The Silesian University of Technology has introduced in 2022 the Gender Equality Plan, a strategic document whose primary objective is to build a diverse working and learning environment free of discrimination and prejudice.

The Plan aims to help identify and overcome further obstacles to Gender Equality, inclusiveness and diversity. It also summarises the experience of recent years, helping to develop specific actions aimed at achieving tangible results in this area in a relatively short period of time. Its implementation, through a systematic series of internally coherent actions over three years from 2022 to 2024 should result in a further reduction in gender inequality and thereby enhance the full participation of all groups in the life of the academic community.

b) Objectives

1. Promotion of an organisational culture based on respect for diversity and appreciation of differences, as well as eliminating gender stereotypes.
2. Support for the balance between career and family life, including the creation of an inclusive work environment and the strengthening of structures that can facilitate the achievement of these goals.
3. Increase of gender balance in decision-making bodies and processes, at different levels of the organisational structure of the Silesian University of Technology.
4. Support for processes that foster equal access to recruitment and career development opportunities, including promotions.
5. Promotion of incorporation of the gender dimension in research, education programmes, courses, and training, and implemented innovations.
6. Raising awareness of issues related to countering various forms of gender-based violence, including sexual harassment.

c) *Implementation*

The objectives and actions forming the essence of the Gender Equality Plan 2022-2024 have been developed by the appointed team on the basis of conclusions from the analysis of quantitative and qualitative data in the areas of employment structure, participation of women and men in decision-making and management bodies, salary levels in the same positions, career and academic development, as well as communication of university-wide Gender Equality experiences.

Implementation of the plan is designed for years 2022-2024 within five specified areas listed below, including development of good practices and recommendations, organisation of trainings and seminars, collection and analysis of gender-specific statistical data etc.

Monitoring of the Gender Equality Plan will be conducted on an annual basis and communicated to members of the University community through a written report on Gender Equality at the University.

Five implementation areas are as follows:

- AREA 1: WORK-LIFE BALANCE, ORGANISATIONAL CULTURE AND COMBATING STEREOTYPES
- AREA 2: GENDER BALANCE IN SENIOR MANAGEMENT POSITIONS AND DECISION-MAKING BODIES
- AREA 3: GENDER BALANCE, GENDER EQUALITY IN RECRUITMENT PROCESSES AND CAREER PROMOTIONS
- AREA 4: INCORPORATION OF THE GENDER DIMENSION IN EDUCATION AND RESEARCH PROGRAMMES
- AREA 5: COMBATING GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE, INCLUDING SEXUAL HARASSMENT

d) *Successes*

The Silesian University of Technology considers Gender Equality a fundamental and inalienable right, which is reflected in the content of numerous internal legal acts. In addition, it was one of the first universities in Poland to implement continuous and consistent policies for Gender Equality, especially in the group of academic staff and doctoral students, receiving the prestigious HR Excellence in Research award in January 2017, confirming the adoption and improvement of its human resources strategy on the basis of the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct for the Recruitment of Researchers. The following years saw the continued adoption of good practices and legislation in this area, taking into account students, as well as administrative, engineering and service staff. Among other things, the university has implemented:

- Policy on Counteracting Mobbing and Discrimination, 2020,
- Policy on Employment of Staff at the Silesian University of Technology, 2021,
- Code of Ethics for Academic Teachers, 2021.

It also established in 2021 bodies for countering mobbing and discrimination, including a Coordinator and Vice Coordinator for Counteracting Mobbing and Discrimination and a Commission for Counteracting Mobbing and Discrimination.

e) Challenges

The survey, conducted in December 2021, revealed the following problems:

- women are significantly more likely to experience various forms of gender-based inequalities, in particular unwelcome jokes, and comments of a sexual nature, questioning of competences and skills on the grounds of gender and different (better or worse) treatment on these grounds, as well as difficulties in combining work and private life,
- lack of knowledge of sexual harassment and other forms of gender-based discrimination,
- the university's procedures and bodies for counteracting mobbing and discrimination are not widely known,
- further research and analysis should be carried out in relation to the group who did not wish to provide information on their gender,
- there are different problems and expectations in terms of Gender Equality depending on the location in the structure of the university community.

f) Recommendations on measures to be taken

All the recommendations and actions are described in depth in the Gender Equality Plan implementation.

3. Contact Point

Office of Vice Rector for Science and Development – Chairman of the Gender Equality Plan Development Team: rn@polsl.pl

4. References

The official document in Polish can be found on the SUT website: <https://www.polsl.pl/hrps/wp-content/uploads/sites/887/2022/06/Plan-Rownosci-Plci-PS-2.pdf>

Summary in English: https://www.polsl.pl/en/ps_aktualnosci/gender-equality-plan-of-the-silesian-university-of-technology-for-2022-2024/

M. Case study 13: EURECA-PRO Alliance 5

University of León, RE-EURECA-PRO

1. Summary

The Universidad de León in Spain (ULE) has a strong commitment for addressing the gender dimension within its researches, teachers, students and the rest of the university staff. In the last years, a series of activities including a concrete Plan has revolutionised what is done at the university, generating a specific organisational structure named “Area of Social Responsibility” and an “Equality Unit” which aims to prepare, promote and supervise the institutional equality policies, particularly in relation to gender. A series of objectives within the “Equality Plan” and concrete actions are reflected in the following paragraphs.

2. Description

a) Context

ULE has a strong commitment to ensure the gender dimension at all levels. In this sense, the University has its own “Equality Plan” (October, 2022) aligned with the UN ODS 5, the European Directives 2010/41/CE, 2006/54/CE and 2004/113/CE, the national legislation (Ley Orgánica 3/2007, Ley 14/2011), the European Agendas regarding the European education common framework, the Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe assessing Gender Equality as a transversal objective in their programmes/projects.

Due to the very nature of their functions, universities and centres of higher education and research are placed in a central position to assume within the framework of their actions, the responsibility of promoting innovation, development and social change. For this reason, they must play a leading role in promoting the equality between its researchers. This “Equality Plan” is applicable to all ULE workers.

ULE has as a transversal service to the whole university community, the “Equality Unit”, which is constituted as an norganisational structure that reports to the Office of the Social Responsibility Vice-Rectorate. Its aim is to prepare, promote and supervise the institutional equality policies, particularly in relation to gender.

Within the Unit, exists the ULE “Equality Commission”, with the following goals:

- a. Make proposals for the preparation of plans, programmes and actions that, in terms of equality, are being developed by this university.
- b. Monitor compliance with the objectives set and the actions carried out, as well as the means and resources used in relation to the established forecasts.
- c. Participate in the equality plans of the university, collaborating both in their preparation and implementation in practice as well as in the evaluation of its results.
- d. Any other that is entrusted to it, within the scope of the objectives of the Equality Unit.

b) Objectives

The “Equality Plan” from ULE has its own objectives, each of which has a series of measures and indicators to evaluate them. Also, they have a time plan to be accomplished. The objectives of this plan have a long-term strategy, as they are constantly being reviewed and updated. Moreover, each objective and measures are constantly developing new actions to permeate the whole ULE community and the society in the city of León.

Objective 1: Collect, analyse and systematise the necessary data using the gender variable to ensure real equality between women and men at ULE.

Objective 2: Raise awareness and make visible the culture in equality by reason of gender at ULE.

Objective 3: Advance in communication on equality.

Objective 4: Guarantee equality by reason of gender in the access, promotion and conditions of provision of services of the staff from ULE.

Objective 5: Promote the culture of conciliation and co-responsibility, promoting the enjoyment of permits and effective reconciliation measures, so that care of minors, the elderly and/or people with disabilities, does not imply a burden on the professional development and women's promotion.

Objective 6: Promote the participation of women in university life.

Objective 7: Prevent and avoid harassment at ULE, especially bullying, sexual and gender-based harassment.

Objective 8: Fight against all types of violence against women at ULE.

Objective 9: Risk assessment employment with a gender perspective.

Objective 10: Continue advancing in compliance with the “Equality Plan”.

Objective 11: Guarantee equality based on gender identity.

c) Implementation

In this section, we would like to highlight some of the actions that have been implemented in line with the policies at ULE.

ACTION 1. The ULE Equality Unit designs gender training targeting the university community. Some of these courses are specially designed for researchers and teaching staff, for example the following course have taken place in the last years:

"Gender perspective inclusion in university teaching practice"

"How to innovate from equality: application of the gender perspective in teaching guides"

"Inclusion of gender analysis in scientific research"

"Harassment and other associated behaviors"

"Health, medicine, science and gender perspective"

"What is non-sexist language and what is it for: Practical application in administrative language"

ACTION 2. Raise awareness on equal gender among researchers. An example of the activities that are carried out is the Conference talk on "The role of women scientists in nanotechnology for health" given by Prof. Laura M. Lechuga, researcher at the Spanish Superior Council of Scientific Research (CSIC) which took place on March 31, 2022 in the ULE Faculty of Biological and Environmental Sciences. She is a referent regarding breaking barriers on the gender dimension. The talk was a great success at ULE and a truly inspiring work for both staff and students. More info about the action and the type of researchers invited to these activities can be found in the following links:

<https://www.unileon.es/noticias/laura-lechuga-hablara-en-la-ule-del-papel-de-las-cientificas-en-la-nanotecnologia>

<https://www.rtve.es/noticias/20220211/laura-lechuga-cientifica-nanotecnologia/2286840.shtml>

ACTION 3. Since 2021, each year ULE has implemented a contest for the best Final Bachelor thesis (TFG), Final Master thesis (TFM) and Doctoral Thesis on Gender Equality with an economic reward. These awards are intended to raise awareness among students on Gender Equality, non-discrimination and non-violence against women.

<https://servicios.unileon.es/area-de-accesibilidad-y-apoyo-social/premios-igualdad-de-genero/>

d) *Successes*

Since the creation of the "Equality Unit" as an entity, and the document "Equality Plan", ULE has been proactive in this area. The number of activities to increase the gender dimension within the ULE has not stopped.

e) *Challenges*

One of the main challenges is achieving penetration to all levels of the institution and in all areas of knowledge. Moreover, the gender dimension in R&I is also starting to permeate the teaching courses at the different Faculties, however, a bigger impulse in this sense is to be taken.

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

The main recommendation is to continue working and consolidating the actions that are being taken within the university, always with a long-term perspective, assuring quality of the actions and permeability to all academic stages and areas of knowledge.

3. Contact Point

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4. References

<https://servicios.unileon.es/area-de-accesibilidad-y-apoyo-social/unidad-de-igualdad/>

[https://servicios.unileon.es/area-de-accesibilidad-y-apoyo-social/files/2022/12/Plan de Igualdad ULE.pdf](https://servicios.unileon.es/area-de-accesibilidad-y-apoyo-social/files/2022/12/Plan_de_Igualdad_ULE.pdf)

N. Case study 14: FilmEU Alliance

1. Summary

The higher education institutions participating in FilmEU_RIT have started to develop the knowledge of their researchers in respect of the gender dimension in research. In the first instance, this has been through existing programmes targeted at academic and research staff and doctoral candidates, in the context of institutional commitments to equality. Institutions draw upon expertise, including that which has emerged out of previous EU-funded projects which generated resources and toolkits, ensuring that researchers, including at early career stages, are familiar with the significance of the gender dimension. These initial steps inform the decision of FilmEU_RIT to include a specific, more ambitious and Alliance-level training programme in its proposals for further funding, in the context of a renewed commitment to diversity, inclusiveness and Gender Equality in the FilmEU Mission Statement (2023) and the successful application for funding for the WIDERA project 'WIRE FilmEU' commencing January 2024.

2. Description

a) Context

FilmEU_RIT's research community involves a wide range of researchers – some with doctoral qualifications and/or a specific research function within their contract, others at an early stage (e.g. pursuing a doctorate, including through artistic research), and many who have very substantial teaching and creative practice experience now seeking to develop a research component to their career. The gender dimension in research is recognised as important across the higher education institutions, but there is a need to do more to equip the research community with the relevant skills – especially as they participate in joint activities at the Alliance level and/or seek to develop proposals for projects (including seeking EU support).

b) Objectives

- To encourage FilmEU_RIT researchers to engage with training in respect of the gender dimension in research.
To ensure that the FilmEU_RIT community has a higher level of awareness of the gender dimension, so as to inform (for instance) the conduct of research pilots, the development of new collaborations, and the preparation of funding applications.

c) Implementation

Researchers took part in programmes offered in the participating institutions, as follows:

UL: UL's Gender and Diversity Plan comprehends five axes identified as priority and central, at national, European and international levels: Balance between personal, family, professional life and the organisational culture; Gender balance/diversity in leadership and decision making; Gender Equality/diversity in recruitment and career advancement; Integration of the gender

dimension/diversity in research and innovation; Measures to fight prejudice, gender inequality and harassment. Specifically, a commitment was made to increase the scientific collection of the institution and include the topics of inclusion and diversity in the training and research agenda of the institution, linked to participation in projects that ensure Gender Equality and diversity. To implement this, a workshop on “gender and diversity awareness: presentation of the internal diagnostic results” was held on 30/11/2022. A further training activity is scheduled to happen on 14/07/2023 under the topic “Gender and Diversity in the Higher Education Sector: Measures, Practices and Challenges”. This complements a number of projects dedicated to gender, feminism and diversity at the unit CICANT (where FilmEU_RIT researchers are concentrated), e.g. <https://www.futurefilm.education/> <https://femable.eu> and <https://www.restarteuropa.org/>

IADT: IADT recently received the Athena Swan ‘Bronze’ accreditation for its commitment to Gender Equality. The action plan adopted as part of this process made specific recognition of the need to support and develop the gender dimension in research, with measurable commitments adopted and assigned to the managers responsible for equality, diversity and inclusion and for research. As such, the workshop ‘Integrating gender in research’ on the sex/gender dimension in research, facilitated by Dr. Maxime Forest (Yellow Window) and utilising the Gender in EU-Funded Research Toolkit, was held on 03/02/2023, with substantial promotion across the campus research community. 6 FilmEU_RIT researchers completed the workshop and are able to utilise the findings in e.g. FilmEU_RIT pilot research projects, and in the preparation of proposals for further funding.

TLU: TLU has an elaborate and rigorous Gender Equality plan that includes requirement and remuneration, attention to the gender dimension regarding combining work and family life, equal representation in management, and ways to integrate gender perspective to research, teaching, and learning. The more detailed vision and policy plan can be found here: <https://www.tlu.ee/en/tlu-gender-equality-plan>. Key aspects supporting this agenda in respect of the gender perspective in research include the hosting of the Estonian Women’s Studies and Resource Centre, and support for the professional development of lecturers / researchers.

d) Successes

High quality training is available through recognised experts, and can be offered to researchers at a key stage of their development e.g. as they, through the opportunities provided by FilmEU_RIT, seek to become more research-active and also engage in projects where the gender dimension is a required component (e.g. Horizon Europe proposals).

e) Challenges

Many researchers did not have formal training in respect of the gender dimension as part of, for instance, their own doctoral programme.

There has been more limited engagement with these opportunities on the part of male researchers.

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

Continue to ensure FilmEU_RIT researchers engage with existing training and development opportunities

Secure funding to deliver Alliance-level training and development in this respect (including, subject to funding and eligibility, support for knowledge and capacity in the four institutions joining the FilmEU Alliance, three of whom are from Widening countries).

Work with experts to explore whether courses and workshops in this regard can also address any applicable specificities or unique features of the gender dimension in *artistic* research – collaborating as appropriate with other Alliances (existing and in the process of creation).

Monitor the number of researchers who have been trained including reference to demographics as appropriate (e.g. gender, career stage).

Seek that the FilmEU inclusivity plan / DEI policy makes reference to the training and development of researchers in respect of the gender dimension as an aspect of implementation, and include firm targets in the proposed joint Gender and Equality Plan which is a deliverable in the future project WIRE.

3. *Contact Point*

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4. *References*

N/A

O. Case study 15: NeurotechEU Alliance 1

1. Summary

The NeurotechEU, the European University of Brain and Technology, represents an Alliance of nine European universities with a focus on neurotechnology. From its inception, the Alliance was designed to prioritise Gender Equality, with a decision-making team already established in a gender-balanced manner. The strategic vision of the Alliance is centred around the core objective of *"Fostering diversity, Gender Equality, and inclusiveness in research and innovation for an equitable workforce and sustainable growth."*

2. Description

a) Context

Gender Equality in research and innovation is a cross-cutting priority reiterated by the European Commission with the launch of Horizon Europe (2021), entirely in alignment with the European Commission Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, which sets out the Commission's broader commitment to equality across all EU policies. The goal is to improve the European research and innovation system, create gender-equal working environments where all talents can thrive and better integrate the gender dimension in projects to improve research quality and the relevance to society of the knowledge, technologies and innovations produced.

Specifically, with the launch of Horizon Europe as critical funding programme for research and innovation, Gender Equality is addressed at three main levels:

- Having a Gender Equality Plan (GEP) in place is an eligibility criterion for legal entities applying as beneficiaries and affiliated entities to this EU programme.
- The integration of a gender dimension into research and innovation content is a requirement by default.
- The added objective of increasing gender balance throughout the programme, with a target of 50% women in Horizon Europe related boards, expert groups and evaluation committees, and gender balance among research teams set as a ranking criterion for proposals with the same score.

On the other hand, the priority of the commitment to Gender Equality is also reiterated in the ERA policy agenda for 2022–2024, where the European Commission emphasises the need to address gender-based violence in academic settings and to open up Gender Equality policies to inclusiveness, intersections with other diversity categories, and potential grounds for discrimination such as ethnicity, disability or sexual orientation.

Gender inequality in research and education

Only a fraction of female students selects Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) related fields in higher education. International female enrollment is particularly low in specific areas. For example, around 3% of students joining information and communication technology (ICT) courses across the globe are women, while for mathematics and statistics courses,

the percentage settles around 5%, increasing to 8% for engineering, manufacturing, and construction courses. Women are more attracted to STEM courses in some regions of the world than others, but the global situation remains characterised by gender imbalances.

On the other hand, women account for a minority of the world's researchers. Thus, despite the growing demand for cross-nationally comparable statistics on women in science, national data and their use in developing policies to address this vital issue often remains limited.

b) Objectives

The main global objective of the Alliance is “*Fostering diversity, Gender Equality and inclusiveness in research and innovation for the equitable workforce and sustainable growth*”. Besides other inclusive goals targeting socioeconomic inequality, access for individuals living with disabilities, etc., the main objectives regarding the gender dimensions focus on reducing the disparities in education and research (leaving the staff in the hands of institutional policies since all members of the Alliance are committed to them).

c) Implementation

In alignment with the critical objective defined above, dedicated work packages have been implemented in both projects NeurotechEU and NeurotechRI (swafs project for NeurotechEU): WP7 *Widening access: diversity, multilingualism and multiculturalism* and WP8 *Quality control and Gender Equality in Science for Innovation* respectively.

NeurotechEU/RI has been approached based on the lessons learned by the Alliance members on their processes of building their previous own Gender Equality strategies and further implementation plans. Consequently, on the process of designing a Gender Equality Strategy for NeurotechEU/RI:

- It is relevant to understand that Gender Equality requires a long-term transformation process that actively examines, challenges, and transforms the underlying causes of gender inequality.
- In this process, co-work is considered a key factor of further successful implementation plans. Therefore, defining a Gender Equality Strategy for NeurotechEU/RI will be a cyclic process where a first version is delivered in the present document, but an updated version will be produced further on after having had conversations with all Alliance key stakeholders, and having therefore gathered a broader and more realistic perspective about barriers and peculiar circumstances to take into account.
- Even though it will be a long-term process, we should be aware of the importance of short-term actions as one of the key successful factors. Thus, both long-term general guidelines and short-term actions are addressed. Those actions can be found in the already submitted Deliverable D8.4 as annexes.
- It involves providing knowledge, techniques, and tools to develop skills and changes in attitudes and behaviours. NeurotechEU/RI Alliance will make use, throughout the project, of the material and tools (GEAR) provided by the European Institute for Gender Equality

(EIGE). In particular, those provided to overcome common challenges and good practices criteria and examples (webinars, videos and other resources).

The Gender Equality Strategy for NeurotechEU/RI also highlights the relevance of being an active stakeholder in the corresponding networking ecosystem. Networking activities between all the Alliance institutions' Gender and Diversity Offices will be promoted focused on spreading Best Practices and reinforcing links between internal and external key stakeholders in this field. Building relevant connections will be a priority to foster quicker and smooth transformations within the Alliance activities and processes.

The NeurotechEU/RI Alliance is composed of a rich diversity, with institutions from countries with Gender Equality Indexes are both below and above the European average (in a range of 53 –91 out of 100 according to the Gender Equality Index 2019-2022). Therefore, NeurotechEU/RI Gender Equality Strategy will emphasise Alliance activities, processes, and functions, also expecting to have an impact from the Alliance individuals to the institutions and societies to which they belong.

d) Successes

Besides an apparent increase of the awareness of the gender dimension in education and research, it is worth mentioning the successful “Women in NeurotechEU” event that aims to empower and support women in science and technology, fostering a more diverse and inclusive community.

Throughout the event, attendees can engage in roundtable discussions, keynote speeches, and networking sessions with female scientists and professionals in neurotechnology.

The NeurotechEU Alliance believes that increasing the representation of women in science and technology is crucial for driving innovation and progress in the field. This event is an opportunity for attendees to not only learn from and connect with successful women in the field but also to gain the tools and resources needed to advance their own careers.

Until now, three editions of the “Women in NeurotechEU” have been held. Due to the COVID19 pandemic, the two first editions were held online with an attendance of more than 600 participants. The 3rd edition (face-to-face) hosted over 50 participants among researchers, students and staff coming from the different partner institutions of the Alliance.

e) Challenges

There is a noticeable gender gap in the STEM field of higher education, not explained by gender underperformance in respective subjects in lower education (e.g., mathematics, science). A visible gender gap tends to appear in the later years of secondary education. One possible issue for this could be the under-representation of female scientists in the media. Furthermore, a report from Harvard Business Review gives valuable insight into the experiences of women in academia, showing that female academics often have their successes discounted and expertise questioned compared to their male peers. Moreover, the “tightrope” effect, where women feel increased pressure to behave in a masculine way as proof of their competency while maintaining their

feminine qualities to be “likable,” exerts higher stress and strain on the feminine gender. The magnitude of the issue reflects in statistics, with 34.1% of female scientists in one survey reporting a perceived pressure to play a traditionally feminine role, while 53.0% reported backlash for displaying stereotypically masculine behaviours (e.g., speaking their minds, being decisive) (Williams,2015). Moreover, maternity bias represents another limitation, with two-thirds of mothers in academia having their commitment and competencies questioned. These inequities foster frustration, anxiety, and unhealthy competition, with women reporting that they “compete with their female colleagues for the ‘woman’s spot’”. The issue is deeply rooted in societal gender norms and expectations, and approaches for mitigation should be integrated at all levels of education and continues well into working life.

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

The "Closing the Gender Gap Accelerator" by the World Forum shares an exciting approach through strategies including the enhancement of social safety nets (e.g., provision of childcare support), as well as encouraging women into management and leadership positions. Some good practices, in the form of financial or social support, include Scientista (campus communities, conferences, online content), Cordis Project (gather, exchange, develop and disseminate ideas of good practices), Girls Who Code (free summer programmes and after-school clubs for teen girls), Girl Geek dinners (social support and community), Golden seeds (financial support), and Million Women Mentors.

NeurotechEU/RI actively supports integrating a more extensive array of student populations, ensuring their success in and beyond higher education. Furthermore, by emulating the different partners' best practices such as gender mainstreaming strategies, integrating Gender Equality work, and fair admission practices, the NeurotechEU Alliance has the opportunity to deliver the promise of inclusion, non-discrimination, equity, and diversity in all educational programmes and related activities across individual partner universities, associate partners, and the consortium as a whole.

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P. Case study 16: NeurotechEU Alliance 2

NeurotechEU Alliance: The Bogazici University case

1. Summary

The Bogazici University (BOUN), Turkey, belongs to the NeurotechEU Alliance and has been working to promote Gender Equality and create an inclusive environment for all students, faculty, and staff. The university has recognised the importance of gender equity and has implemented various initiatives to address this issue.

BOUN has made Gender Equality an integral part of its priorities, implementing various systems and governance structures to advance towards greater equality. The university is firmly committed to promoting equality between women and men and is taking proactive steps to address any lingering forms of inequality.

2. Description

a) Context

BOUN is a prominent institution known for its commitment to academic excellence and social responsibility and has been actively working to promote Gender Equality and create an inclusive environment for all students, faculty, and staff. The university has recognised the importance of gender equity and has implemented various initiatives to address this issue. Moreover, the university fulfills a necessary condition of Gender Equality ranking systems in higher education, like the Times Higher Education rankings, by institutionalising processes and practices for incorporating gender in research.

b) Objectives

The main objectives addressed by the BOUN Gender Equality plan are the following:

- Equalise female representation in research teams and labs
- Training in gender-sensitive research techniques and gender mainstreaming for researchers
- Constructing a structure to incorporate gender issues into a financing system for internal research
- To develop incorporating the gender factor into teaching and curricula
- Training in gender-sensitive teaching techniques and gender mainstreaming for instructors

c) Implementation

Several activities are continuously being developed to reach the above-mentioned objectives, all supervised by the following responsible/supporting units:

- Scientific Research Projects Division
- Vice-Rector of Research
- Vice-Rector of Education

- Commissions

d) *Successes*

The main successes regarding gender dimension in R&I with a long-term impact can be the following:

- **Women's Studies Centre:** BOUN has a Women's Studies Centre that promotes research, education, and public awareness about gender-related issues. The centre organises conferences, seminars, and workshops on topics such as Gender Equality, women's rights, and feminist theory.
- **Gender Studies Programme:** The university offers a Gender Studies Programme that allows students to pursue interdisciplinary studies on gender-related topics. This programme aims to enhance understanding and critical thinking about gender issues and contribute to social change.
- **Support and Counselling Services:** BOUN provides support and counselling services to students, including those related to Gender Equality and women's rights. These services offer guidance and assistance to students who may face challenges or discrimination based on their gender.
- **Student Clubs and Organisations:** There are several student clubs and organisations at BOUN that focus on Gender Equality, feminism, and women's rights. These groups provide platforms for students to engage in discussions, raise awareness, and organise events related to gender-related issues.
- **Training and Workshops:** The university regularly organises training programmes and workshops on gender sensitivity and awareness for students, faculty, and staff. These initiatives aim to promote inclusivity and reduce gender biases within the university community.

e) *Challenges*

Especially in some faculties, women are underrepresented in leadership positions.

Recognising and embracing intersectionality and inclusivity is essential for effective gender mainstreaming efforts in R&I long-term strategies at universities. It involves acknowledging and tackling the interconnected discrimination and marginalisation that individuals may encounter due to various factors, such as their gender identity, race, ethnicity, sexuality, disability, and other social dimensions. An intersectional and inclusive approach is crucial to ensure that gender mainstreaming strategies comprehensively address the diverse experiences and requirements of all individuals, while actively avoiding the perpetuation of additional forms of discrimination.

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

To ensure the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in R&I long-term strategies in universities, it is important to develop a Gender Equality and gender equity policy plan, raise awareness and provide training, integrate gender perspectives in research design, promote gender balance in decision-making bodies, implement inclusive recruitment and evaluation practices, collect and analyse gender-disaggregated data, establish gender-responsive funding mechanisms, and regularly monitor and evaluate progress. These measures collectively contribute to creating an environment that promotes Gender Equality, inclusivity, and evidence-based decision-making in research and innovation.

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https://www.boun.edu.tr/Assets/Documents/Dosyalar/gender_equality_plan.pdf

Q. Case study 17: NeurotechEU Alliance 3

NeurotechEU Alliance: Radboud University case

1. Summary

The Radboud University (RU), in the Netherlands, is the coordinator of the NeurotechEU Alliance and is contributing to a healthy, free world with equal opportunities for all. With this, Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion (DEI) are crucial fundamental principles at Radboud University. Our mission is to contribute to a healthy, free world where everyone has equal access to opportunities. We advocate for an inclusive campus for all staff and students, regardless of race, gender, age, religion, gender identity or expressions, marital or family status, ethnic background, socioeconomic background, ability, or sexual orientation. Inclusion, equity, and cooperation are all bolstered by a robust and welcoming community.

2. Description

a) Context

Radboud University contributes to a healthy, free world with equal opportunities for everyone. We do this as an inclusive university community and diversity principles play a central role for RU. RU sees it as its social responsibility to contribute to the achievement of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) such as those set by the United Nations.

Some of the key SDGs for DEI include: Goal 4 (Quality education), Goal 5 (Gender Equality), Goal 10 (Reduce inequality), Goal 11 (Sustainable cities and communities), Goal 16 (Peace, justice and strong public services) and Goal 17 (partnership to achieve objectives).

b) Objectives

The University's ambition for **Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI)** is to promote a safe, inclusive and equitable academic community that embraces and promotes diversity and the values of social justice, and to advocate for and act for positive change, in line with the Sustainable Development Goals.

This main objective is divided in the following five goals:

- Goal 1: Embedding DEI: Embed DEI in policy and practice tools to drive positive cultural and structural change.
- Goal 2: Monitor DEI: Keep your finger on the pulse.
- Goal 3: Shaping DEI policies and procedures.
- Goal 4: Become a DEI hub: Positioning Radboud University as a catalyst and hub for diversity, equal opportunities and inclusion [DEI]
- Goal 5: Creating an accessible, inclusive and safe campus: The Radboud campus forms an inclusive community and working environment. The barriers that promote inequity are removed. Everyone, including vulnerable and marginalised groups feel represented, respected, recognised, seen, heard and protected.

c) *Implementation*

The University created a DEI's office which mission is to lead, facilitate, guide, encourage, and support all levels of the organisation to achieve diversity, equity and inclusion objectives through collaboration and insightful planning.

Additionally, there was the creation of the two following documents:

- **The Strategic Plan for Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) 2021-2025** of Radboud University reflects conversations and the contributions of the staff, the students and our social partners. In keeping with Radboud's emancipatory roots, the focus is on care for each other and the world around us. The plan shows how DEI acts as a starting point for education, research, and impact. It describes DEI-focused actions through which Radboud University aims to form an open and inspiring community, with opportunities for everyone and space for new forms of thinking, learning and working.
- **The DEI manifesto** has been compiled in addition to the DEI plan. The manifesto includes tips and conditions on how to make your own contribution.

To learn more about the strategic plan and the manifesto, the DEI Office developed an [interactive game](#).

Aligned with the above-mentioned documents, the Gender Equality plan is developed by the DEI office in partnership with the Chief Diversity Officer and Research and Impact division, taking into account the input from various stakeholders across the University.

The actions planned to implement successfully the Gender Equality plan are organised in 5 areas:

- Area 1: Organisational culture and work-life balance
- Area 2: Social safety
- Area 3: Leadership and management
- Area 4: Recruitment, selection and career progression
- Area 5: Gender dimension in research and education

A detailed description of the different actions can be found in the Gender Equality plan.

d) *Successes*

The awareness of the gender dimension is clearly increasing among the university population and the policies and actions taken are generally accepted and adopted.

In 2020, Radboud University had more than 24,000 students and 5,603 staff members (in terms of fulltime equivalent, fte), of whom 56% (3,152 fte) were academic staff and 44% (2,448 fte) were support staff. In December 2020, the share of women among PhD candidates and assistant professors were 49.4% and 46.1% respectively. The share of women among associate professors were 28.7% and the share of women among full professors exceeded 30% for the first time, namely 30.2% (LNVH Women Professors Monitor 2021). Acknowledging the need for further improvement, Radboud University has set a target figure of 36% women professors by 2025 (including Radboud University Medical Centre). Radboud University has steadily occupied

a position among the top four of Dutch universities with regard to the proportion of women professors and the number of women professors is continuously growing.

Several specific initiatives had/have great acceptance. As for example the **DEI Unconscious Bias Theatre Workshops**:

In a joint diversity equity and inclusion (DEI) initiative, Radboud & Radboud University have created an interactive theatre with Crux Creatives. Input for the script was provided by staff and students. The shared narratives make this authentic production an exercise in reflection. This workshop offers the audience, leaders and team members, opportunities to address serious issues that they encounter in their workplace and allow them to engage in difficult conversations. The scenes act as windows into prejudice, everyday behaviour and issues of Gender Equality and breaking the glass ceiling; physical or psychological limitations that (un)consciously lead to distance from the labour market and construction of barriers when it comes to individuals with different identities. It seeks to give individuals the tools to sit with discomfort in a safe space.

e) Challenges

Gender is often interrelated to other social categories, such as ethnicity, functional impairment, age, sexual orientation, and social class. An intersectional approach acknowledges these interrelations and the diversity within gender, for example, non-binary, cisgender and transgender. Such an intersectional approach is relevant in how it informs, influences and promotes Gender Equality. To this end, Radboud University intends to incorporate a gender approach that recognises intersectionality.

f) Recommendations on measures to be taken

Recommendations extracted from our experience are:

- 1) Continue with ongoing actions to promote well-being, social safety, and a sense of belonging among staff and students through workshops, facilities input, and posters.
- 2) New policies addressing marginalisation and discrimination, revisions to the Code of Conduct from a gender perspective, and revised forms for accessibility and accommodations.
- 3) Continuing an efficient complaints process and supporting confidential advisors with tools for addressing issues from a gender perspective and applying a restorative justice approach.
- 4) Raising awareness about social and psychological safety, gender-based discrimination and violence through training, forming affinity groups and social safe space networks, and organising workshops on inclusive and safe classrooms for teaching staff.
- 5) Strengthening leadership skills and knowledge on diversity, equity, and inclusion in practice through conducting studies and providing advanced modules on anti-bias training for leadership.

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- DEI strategic plan: <https://www.ru.nl/sites/default/files/2023-01/Plan-DEI-EN-2022.pdf>
- DEI Manifesto: <https://www.ru.nl/sites/default/files/2023-01/Radboud-Dei-Manifeso.pdf>
- DEI interactive game: <https://radbouddei.frisseblikken-narrativegame.com/welcome>
- Gender Equality plan: <https://www.ru.nl/sites/default/files/2023-04/Gender-Equality-Plan-Radboud-University.pdf>
- LNVH Women Professors Monitor 2021: <https://www.lnvh.nl/monitor2021/EN.html>

R. Case study 18: NeurotechEU Alliance 4

NeurotechEU Alliance: The University of Lille case

1. Summary

The University of Lille (ULille), France, belongs to the NeurotechEU Alliance and has been making Gender Equality an integral part of its preoccupations, setting up various systems and governance arrangements to help them move towards greater equality.

ULille intends to reaffirm its political will to promote equality between women and men and give itself the means to act on all forms of inequality that may persist.

Through a range of initiatives and measures, ULille is reducing inequalities between women and men and is combating all forms of discrimination. In order to implement, within its areas of competence, the principles set out in the Interministerial Convention for Equality between Girls and Boys, Women and Men in the Education System, ULille undertakes to define its Gender Equality policy and to publicise it. This policy concerns both students and all staff, as well as all areas of activity in which the university is involved.

2. Description

a) Context

Reducing professional inequality between women and men requires a systemic approach, touching on all aspects, small and large discriminations that lead to structural inequality. From this point of view, ULille is not particularly different from other higher education and research establishments and the institution is not more unequal than many others, and in some respects even performs better.

b) Objectives

To adopt the view that inequalities are the result of multiple factors, some of which are not specifically related to the operation of our institution (guidance, parenthood, for example). Taken this precaution, and ultimately regardless of any legal obligation, ULille sets as collective responsibility to do everything to reduce inequalities.

c) Implementation

ULille is adopting the approach calling for "institutional change" advocated by various studies and research and widely taken up within the European Union by the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE) in partnership with the European Commission, as an essential provision for effectively reducing inequalities: "Institutional change is a strategy for removing obstacles to Gender Equality within the research system itself, and for adapting institutional practices accordingly. In this approach, the focus is on the organisation".

The five axes that will make up this systemic approach are the following:

- 1) Strengthen the governance of equality policies

- **2)** Creating the conditions for equal access to professions and professional responsibilities
- **3)** Eliminate pay and career development gaps
- **4)** Provide better support for maternity, parenthood and the work-life balance
- **5)** Strengthen the prevention of and fight against sexual and gender-based violence

For each of these areas, ULille has proceeded in three stages:

- carrying out a deep diagnosis and objectivising the situation in relation to national or previous data, in order to evaluate both the current gaps and the dynamics;
- definition of the measures to be implemented over three years, the maximum duration of this professional equality plan;
- translate these objectives into indicators to measure progress. These indicators will have to meet SMART (Specific, Measurable, Attainable, Realistic, Time-related) measurement constraints.

Besides this approach to those 5 axes, several other new projects have been launched that have mobilised all users and staff to implement structural equality:

- Sensibilisation sessions for students and various in-house training sessions offered to all staff categories (academic and non-academic)
- A strategic committee at the institution
- Raising awareness of menstrual insecurity and the taboo surrounding menstruation
- Information and awareness-raising programme against gender-based and sexual violence
- Adoption of a charter for equality between women and men
- Deconstructing gender stereotypes
- Making women more visible
- Equality weeks and months
- Inclusive writing
- Etc.

d) Successes

In the university, the measures taken to ensure the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in R&I long-term strategies have demonstrated promising signs of success. Several key indicators highlight the effectiveness of these measures: increased awareness, positive feedback from the community and engagement and a successful policy integration and alignment.

The University of Lille is setting up the "University with a big 'she'" (*L'université avec un grand Elles*)" operation, which aims to find traces in the institution's archives of the long history and importance of the presence of women at the University of Lille. These archives allow us to study the evolution of the status of women at the University by tracing the career paths of female researchers, administrative staff, students, etc. in order to show both the progress made and the way in which the University of Lille has approached its female members over the course of its history.

<https://www.univ-lille.fr/universite/connaitre-les-engagements-qui-nous-guident/responsabilite-sociale/egalite-femmes-hommes/luniversite-avec-un-grand-elles>

e) Challenges

Ensuring the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in research and innovation (R&I) long-term strategies in universities can be a complex and multifaceted task. Several challenges may arise in this process.

- Gender bias and stereotypes
- Lack of gender-disaggregated data
- Underrepresentation of women in leadership positions
- Unconscious biases in recruitment and evaluation processes
- Insufficient gender expertise and knowledge
- Limited institutional support and resources

f) Recommendations on measures to be taken

Besides the general recommendations that can be developed, a Gender Equality policy plan, raise awareness and provide training, integrate gender perspectives in research design, promote gender balance in decision-making bodies, implement inclusive recruitment and evaluation practices, etc. we highly recommend the following points:

- Collect gender-disaggregated data: Develop mechanisms to collect and analyse gender-disaggregated data related to R&I activities. This data should include information on participation rates, funding allocations, research outputs, and career progression. Regularly monitor and evaluate the data to identify gender disparities and inform evidence-based decision-making.
- Establish gender-responsive funding mechanisms: Design funding mechanisms that promote Gender Equality in R&I. This can include allocating specific funding streams for research projects that address gender-related issues or incorporate gender analysis. Ensure that evaluation criteria for funding applications are gender-sensitive and unbiased.
- Monitor and evaluate progress: Regularly monitor and evaluate the progress of gender mainstreaming efforts. Set targets and indicators to assess the impact of interventions and policies. Use the evaluation findings to inform future strategies and make necessary adjustments to ensure continuous improvement.

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4. References

- European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights, and in particular Articles 14 and 17
- Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union, and in particular Articles 7, 9, 20, 21, 23, 31, 33 and 41;
- Constitution of 4 October 1958, and in particular Article 1er;
- Preamble to the Constitution of 27 October 1946, and in particular paragraph 3 ;
- Law no. 83-634 of 13 July 1983 on the rights and obligations of civil servants, articles 6 to 6 quinties, 8 bis, 9 bis, 11, 16 bis, 21, 21 bis and 25, together with Law no. 84-16 of 11 January 1984 on statutory provisions relating to the civil service;
- Education Code, and in particular articles L121-1 and L712-2 ;
- Law of 27 January 2017 on equality and citizenship, article 170 et seq;
- Circular of 8 July 2013 on the implementation of the memorandum of understanding of 8 March 2013 on professional equality between women and men in the civil service ;
- Circular of 9 March 2018 on combating sexual and gender-based violence in the civil service;
- Charter for equality between women and men drawn up and ratified on 29 January 2013 by the Conférence des Présidents d'Université (CPU), the Conférence des Directeurs des Ecoles Françaises d'Ingénieurs (CDEFI) and the Conférence des Grandes Ecoles (CGE);
- Agreement of 30 November 2018 on professional equality between women and men in the civil service

5. Case study 19: RUN-EU Alliance

1. Summary

The RUN-European University (RUN-EU) has implemented strategies to strengthen our human capital resources in research and innovation (R&I) across our university network and adopts a gender participatory approach to ensure the equal distribution of resources and power. In addition, RUN, through the project's objectives and tasks, ensure the equal possibilities to all its participants and target groups to have and make an impact. As part of our Research Career Development Programme, we have established a Gender and Diversity Ambassador Network (GDA) to support, encourage and advocate for women in R&I and career advancement within the RUN-EU participant network, following commission recommendations on gender balance and equality. Furthermore, we have introduced a Research Career Evaluation System to reward researchers and research excellence at all career development stages.

2. Description

a) Context

RUN-EU has a strong vibrant gender-balanced consortium membership including Presidents, Vice-Presidents, and steering group members. The project's partners and target groups are transdisciplinary from the start. Equal opportunities for all are ensured by openness and a participatory approach. The project follows the Human Rights-Based Approach (HRBA),⁸ which is a conceptual framework based on international human rights standards. By following this framework, the project can better analyse and prevent all discrimination based on, for example age, race, gender or disability. Monitoring the process towards Gender Equality in science has become a well-established activity of the EU research policy. By adopting these principles, our approach is fully in line with Directive 2002/73/EC of the European Parliament⁹ and of the Council on the implementation of the principle of equal treatment of genders as regards access to employment, working conditions, vocational training and promotion. Ensuring excellent research is acknowledged to be vastly improved by investing in researchers' talents, skills and career development. It is widely acknowledged that human capital is a critical factor in reaping economic and social rewards from investment in research. We have developed a Research Career Development Programme adhering to the principles of the European Charter and Code to support our researchers in identifying clear personal career paths which will encourage inter-sectoral and international mobility during their careers. This programme is supported by the RUN-EU work plan specifically within WP4 (European Mobility Innovation Center) and WP5 (RUN-EU Discovery Programme) researcher mobility and internship programmes. The project and its partners are committed to ensuring Gender Equality in all the phases of the project from planning to implementation.

⁸ <https://unsdg.un.org/2030-agenda/universal-values/human-rights-based-approach>

⁹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2002:269:0015:0020:EN:PDF>

b) Objectives

We acknowledge that there is a gender imbalance in certain areas of the R&I landscape particularly in science and engineering and Gender Equality is considered a core component of our project. RUN-EU has adopted a gender participatory approach to ensure the equal distribution of resources and power, as well as to ensure equal possibilities to ensure all participants and target groups have the opportunity to make an impact through the project's objectives and tasks.

Gender and Diversity Action Plan	
Action	Objectives
Gender and Diversity ambassadors	Promote awareness of the opportunities within R&I. Develop gender-inclusive and awareness discussion forums and focus events amongst the R&I communities.
Aim for a gender balance target of a minimum of 40% female and 40% male participants in our structured master's and PhD research programmes by 2023.	Increase the gender balance of students in our structured postgraduate R&I programmes particularly science and engineering.
Equality & Diversity (including Gender Equality) is a regular item for discussion at RUN-EU PLUS Management Meetings	There is a need to ensure that gender diversity and equality is integrated into all processes and decision made. Annual audit analysis of gender inclusiveness across the R&I programmes of the consortium will be undertaken by RUN-EU PLUS management committee.
To apply effective approaches such as the use of a gender decoder software to ensure the wording of all research advertisements has no gender bias. Expand statement on relevant job advertisements to particularly encourage applications from female candidates.	Advertisements for R&I programmes and other RUN-EU PLUS posts to include the statement that RUN-EU PLUS consortium is an equal opportunities employer, working towards creating and sustaining an inclusive environment which promotes equality, embraces diversity and is committed to family-friendly policies for all.
Research Career Development Programme	Deployment of human resource strategies adhering to the principles of the European Charter and Code to support researchers in identifying clear personal career paths. Commission recommendations on gender balance and equality to address gender

	issues concerning career progression in research encouraging inter-sectoral and international mobility during their careers is being implemented.
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c) *Implementation*

The consortium ensures the presence of gender balance in the technical and management teams and on decision boards implemented to govern the project. As part of our Research Career Development Programme within the RUN-EU PLUS project, a Gender & Diversity Ambassador Network (GDA) has been setup. This network has been developed to support, encourage and advocate for Gender Equality in research and innovation and career advancement within the RUN-EU network, following European Commission recommendations on gender balance and equality. Each RUN-EU Alliance partner has nominated 1 Gender & Diversity ambassador based on their expertise in the field of gender and diversity and who are in some way linked to or part of a research group within their own organisations. These ambassadors connect the European University Alliance members with regional, national, and European agencies to maximise the impact of activities. GDA meet regularly to exchange best practice and mutual learning within the Alliance. They also inform the Rectors and Presidents of the RUN-EU Alliance members about the most relevant issues, while helping in the development of new measures and best practices to be adopted and used.

The GDA network has undertaken many activities to advocate for gender mainstreaming:

- Representation at EU Workshops - the network actively engages in discussions at EU workshops to raise awareness and promote gender diversity. A workshop on Gender and Equality Plans in the R&I Sector was held on 24th of May 2022. The main success factors and barriers to developing and implementing GEPs in R&I institutions was discussed and best practices and learnings shared. The workshop gave participants a platform to share experiences, knowledge and best practices with other universities and professionals across Europe.
- GAP Analysis - an Audit and Gap Analysis was carried out where the Ambassadors have identified whether and how Gender Equality is being addressed within their own organisation. Subsequently, the extent to which existing policy influences the facilitation of researchers, the accessibility of (doctoral) research was analysed as well as systemic differences between men and women in opportunities to do research. In most of the RUN-EU Universities, Gender and Diversity issues have been considered. For example, having a Gender and Diversity Manager as part of the selection committee and by implementing Gender Equality Action Plans within the organisation. Some plans have very specific guidelines regarding working conditions, access to employment, parenting, harassment and how to raise awareness on gender issues and diversity in curricula and research.
- Regular meetings - the GDA network meets regularly, demonstrating strong commitment to advancing equality and diversity within RUN-EU. By consistently meeting, the group

maintains a collective focus on driving positive change. The extent to which institutions are engaged in awareness-raising processes focused on both topics and methodology of research with regard to biases, conscious or not, or unrecognised, implicit assumptions regarding gender differences in the entire research process is a main focus.

d) *Successes*

RUN-EU has achieved notable successes to date in their plans to promote gender and diversity within their organisations and across the RUN-EU network. The implemented strategies have played an important role in fostering a culture of awareness and understanding and have strengthened our human capital resources in research and innovation (R&I).

e) *Challenges*

The need for a co-ordinated approach on best practice sharing between the consortium and a necessity for an integrated long-term agreed joint gender inclusiveness strategy across the network and co-ordinated support systems linking organisational outputs with societal challenges have been identified as challenges across the Alliance members.

It takes time for networks to be consolidated. The foundational work of the Gender and Diversity Ambassador Network puts it in a strong position to build on this work in the coming years. This requires ongoing time commitment and coordination of the network to ensure that the learnings from the network are embedded within all member institutions.

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

Promoting research opportunities in the field of gender diversity and a facilitation of increased participation from women doing research were identified as actions to be implemented by the GDA network.

Regarding, training programmes for all RUN-EU researchers, programme and workshop organisers are encouraged to ensure gender and diversity themes as the crosscutting theme in the training materials where possible.

3. Contact Point

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T. Case study 20: Transform4Europe Alliance

University of Silesia in Katowice, Transform4European Research & Innovation – T4ERI

1. Summary

In the framework of the implementation of the Gender Equality Plan, two competitions were introduced at the University of Silesia in Katowice to improve Gender Equality and promote diversity in research: a call for the best thesis on the theme of equality and diversity and an internal research excellence initiative grant competition. Both aim at raising awareness, engaging the whole academic community and promoting excellent research in the area of gender and diversity.

Both initiatives have a great potential for mainstreaming the gender dimension in research; however, more has to be done in communication and awareness raising in order to engage the whole community.

2. Description

a) Context

Gender and diversity continue to be a challenge in academia both in Western Europe and in Central and Eastern European countries. The University of Silesia in Katowice aims at improving Gender Equality and promoting diversity within the organisation and at enhancing the academic community at a research-informed area of gender and diversity. In order to implement these goals, the Gender Equality Plan Implementation Team has developed two research initiatives as follows: (1) a call for the best thesis on the theme of equality and diversity and (2) an internal research excellence initiative grant competition.

b) Objectives

Research initiatives premise to attract attention of the whole research community and scholars on different levels of their academic career (R1 - R4) to conduct excellent scientific research in the area of gender and diversity. Such an initiative serves as an effective instrument for diagnosis, promotion and research impact in the area of gender and diversity. The competitions are part of the activities implementing the Gender Equality Plan adopted in 2021 at the University of Silesia.

c) *Implementation of the research initiative no. 1 (call for the best thesis on the theme of equality and diversity)*

The competition was developed by the Gender Equality Plan Implementation Team and announced in the Rector's Order 131/ 2022. Works for the competition could be submitted by either the author/s or the thesis supervisor/promoter. The competition was decided in February 2023. 17 works meeting the competition requirements were submitted. The results of the competition were published at www.us.edu.pl

d) *Success and justification of the research initiative no. 1*

In the justification of the competition committee one can read: "The awarded and distinguished works not only meet all the competition criteria, but in addition meet them to a high and very high degree. They are testimony to a deep knowledge of the issues described and analysed, a reflective attitude to the problems raised and research maturity. These works address humanistic, social and legal issues that are important from the point of view of contemporary science, related to various aspects of the functioning of people at risk of exclusion due to gender, sexuality, age, neurodiversity and other characteristics. These works not only reproduce the contemporary picture of knowledge, but with commitment co-create it. They recognise maturing social problems, such as the lack of in-depth knowledge regarding the diagnosis of autism spectrum disorders, the lack of systemic care for people on the spectrum, legal discrimination against people belonging to the LGBTQ+ community, or the dangers of appropriating human rights achievements through the capitalist practices of modern states. They postulate key solutions from the point of view of modernity: prohibition of discrimination by respecting basic human rights, care for building sensitive communication, developing attentiveness, protecting intimacy in relationships with others, freedom of artistic expression." The award ceremony held on March 8, 2023 was linked to a debate entitled "Issues of equality and diversity in education and research - opportunities and limitations," with the participation of female scientists of the University of Silesia, supervisors and promoters of the awarded works and people from the Equality and Diversity Commission.

Further editions of the competition are planned.

e) *Implementation of the research initiative no. 2 (internal research excellence initiative grant competition)*

The "Equality and Diversity in Research" competition was organised as part of the University of Silesia in Katowice's Research Excellence Initiative programme and the University's Gender Equality Plan. It contributes to promoting the topic of equality and diversity in scientific research, disseminating the results of such research, and developing international research cooperation on these issues. It is geared towards activities in line with the EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025 and to increase the relevance and visibility of the University of Silesia, especially in the Horizon Europe programme.

Researchers can apply for funding of up to PLN 10,000 for research activities as well as other activities. The period of implementation of research activities is a maximum of 12 months. The call for applications was held until 15.02.2023.

Female and male scientists representing 11 disciplines received support for such activities as: own research, research and consultation trips, queries, participation in international conferences, development of artistic works, translation and proofreading of texts for publication in high-scoring journals. The applications were evaluated by reviewers representing the applicants' disciplines or related disciplines taking into account the following criteria: compatibility of the

research topic with the objectives of the competition, originality of the research issue, scientific significance/value of the project, social impact, substantive value of the research activity, publication effect, international research cooperation. Out of 47 applications, 18 were recommended for funding.

The funded applications represent the following disciplines: philosophy (1), linguistics (1), literary studies (3), cultural and religious sciences (1), earth sciences (1), pedagogy (3), law (2), psychology (3), sociology (1), fine arts (1), theology (1). A total of almost 100,000 zlotys was allocated for the projects, with the lowest amount of funding being 2,500 zlotys and the highest 8,000 zlotys.

f) Challenges

- Limited interest related to the lack of many specialists in the subject.
- Need to stimulate promotion and awareness of researchers in this area.

g) Recommendations on measures to be taken

Awareness raising and communication are important to promote the active participation of the whole community.

3. Contact Point

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U. Case study 21: UNIC Alliance 1

1. Summary

This case study seeks to identify success stories within the framework of the UNIC Alliance, and more specifically by highlighting the case of the University of Deusto in the implementation of (R&I) long-term strategies, with a special focus on practices and measures taken to ensure the mainstreaming of gender dimension in research and teaching and highlighting some of the main barriers. UNIC's aim is to unlock a truly European experience for a new generation of students who will advance the post-industrial transformations of cities. Cities often exhibit marked inequality of income distribution because of the contrasts between those who are appropriately skilled—professionals, managers, administrators, and those in high-technology service industries—and the poorly paid service workers who look after their needs, together with the unemployed (Oxford Reference Dictionary). Aware of these implications, the UNIC Alliance has included in its activities events that have addressed gender implications from different perspectives. In addition, one of its members, the University of Deusto, has coordinated the GEARING Roles project (H2020), which has been highlighted by the EC as a good practice. This case study summarises some of its main contributions.

2. Description

a) Context

Linking up with the broader focus of UNIC on inclusion, impact, and mobility, UNIC has developed a research and innovation structure around the core concept of 'engaged research'. Engaged research offers an interdisciplinary approach and method for systematic knowledge production for society, but also with and within society. Gender Equality is a fundamental principle of social justice and human rights. It upholds the idea that all individuals, regardless of their gender, should have equal opportunities, freedoms, and protections under the law. Post-industrial societies aspire to be inclusive and fair, and Gender Equality is an essential component of achieving these goals. By promoting Gender Equality, societies can combat discrimination, eliminate gender-based violence, and ensure equal access to healthcare, education, and social services. For this reason, in addition to organising ad hoc events to address these issues, UNIC is committed to gender mainstreaming in the context of this "committed research". One of the members of the Alliance that has stood out for its role in this mainstreaming and in contributing to the objectives of the European Research Area is the University of Deusto, especially through its work in GEARING Roles. The results presented here can be extrapolated to the rest of the institutions and constitute a good practice, recognised by the EU, in the achievement of a more egalitarian research area.

b) Objectives

The objectives of this case study are:

- To analyse the contribution that the results of GEARING Roles make to the partnership.

- To make visible the strategies and tools used to mainstream gender in research and teaching.
- To summarise the main resistances and obstacles identified in the project and which are common to most higher education institutions.

c) *Implementation*

As we have already mentioned, UNIC's interest in making visible the relevance of the gender perspective in post-industrial cities has been reflected in the organisation of different events:

- 6 June 2023: Gender and equality from an institutional perspective. Strategies and actions
- 2nd March 2022: seminar on Equality and Diversity in Post-Industrial Landscapes.

These two events respond to the 5 areas in which universities seek to scale up their contribution to the agenda of reviewing post-industrial cities from a gender perspective, one of them being research and local development (Upp Foundation (2020) Extending civic engagement to postindustrial towns, Universities' role in levelling up and building back better, Part II A report from the UPP Foundation October 2020). Furthermore, as we have mentioned, aware of the importance and relevance of Gender Equality for committed research, UNIC wishes to highlight the experience of its partner the University of Deusto and the work carried out in the GEARING Roles project and in the interdisciplinary gender platform, as a key tool to foster the mainstreaming of the gender perspective in research.

GEARING-Roles aimed at challenging and transforming gender roles and identities linked to professional careers and working towards real institutional change. Apart from the impact that the project implementation is having in all the GEP implementing institutions, project actions are also contributing to knowledge production and exchange through the production of academic outputs, the organisation and participation of events and the training of Early Career Researchers (PhD candidates) linked to the project (4). Over the course of the four-year project, the partners and implementing institutions have accomplished remarkable achievements. Significant progress has been made by all implementing partners in their Gender Equality Plans (GEPs), which have received institutional approval. These GEPs are being actively implemented through various measures, such as adopting diverse recruitment practices, integrating gender perspectives into teaching and research, providing leadership training, offering mentoring programmes, and addressing issues of sexual and gender-based harassment. In addition to these advancements, the project has collaborated closely with other initiatives to promote its broader mission. Through online campaigns, joint events, and shared blog posts, the project has effectively disseminated its message to a wide range of audiences. Notably, the project's Nobel Run game has played a significant role in reaching diverse communities. Nobel Run is an engaging deck-building game that features renowned female scientists. Players assume the role of managing a research team, hiring individuals at different career stages, publishing articles, and securing funding through international projects, all with the ultimate goal of winning a Nobel Prize. The project's dissemination and communication activities have been extensive, effectively raising awareness and engaging a broad audience. The innovative approach of the Nobel Run game has contributed to the project's success in reaching individuals and communities beyond

traditional channels, facilitating dialogue and fostering interest in the pursuit of Gender Equality in the scientific field (López Belloso 2022).

d) Successes

The University of Deusto coordinated the Gearing Roles project, highlighted as “best practice” among the “sister project community” and awarded as project of the month in May 2022.

Some of the main outputs from the project:

- [The Nobel Run Board game](#): Nobel Run is a deck-building game in which players, with the help of some world-famous female scientists, must manage a research team, hire predocs, postdocs and seniors, publish articles and get funding through international projects, all with the overarching aim to win a Nobel Prize. By December 2022 5,378 units of the game have been distributed throughout Spain. Internationally, games^o have been sent to the USA, Australia, Canada, Brazil, New Zealand, the Philippines, South Korea, Chile, Mexico, China, Japan..., although mainly to Europe.

To ease its distribution and use in schools, dynamics have been developed in schools to work on the scientific worksheets (for example, in La Salle Bilbao). Moreover, the game has been presented in Madrid (FNAC Callao and InterOcio game fair), in Bilbao (Casa del Libro) and Girona (Ludivers game fair). In addition, Tranjis Games is taking it to the main gaming fairs it attends as a publisher, showing how assistants play the game. The European Commission also launched a dissemination campaign by raffling games. This resulted in the game being included in the rankings as one of the best-selling games.

The biographies of the scientists have been published in open access in English. A paper booklet has also been produced and is available for open download in both Spanish and English. Small video clips have been made to narrate the lives of the women scientists on Instagram to bring their lives closer to a younger audience. Furthermore, the game has been acknowledged for its contribution to social impact: it has received the second Aristos Campus Mundus Good Practices in University Social Commitment Award and recently it has been nominated as finalist in the Best Family Game by a Spanish Author category of the Corona Lúdica Awards. The winning games will be announced on 4 March at the Salón del Cómic de Valencia.

- [The Humorarium](#): The Humorarium is a toolkit with arguments and vignettes that were designed using feminist humour, aiming to support Gender Equality stakeholders in their effort to combat resistance to change, in the context of research performing organisations. It aims to showcase how feminist art and humour can be powerful means to reach different groups of people and promote equality in a light and effective way for topics that could be perceived as contentious. In order to encourage reflection and active participation on the subject of sexism and Gender Equality in academia, it provides counter-arguments to build your case for Gender Equality in academia, a set of recommendations addressed to individuals and policy-makers, and a list of inspiring ideas and activities for the use of vignettes to further embrace the use of feminist humour in the context of academia.

- The [Deusto Guidelines for gender mainstreaming in teaching and research](#): The Guidelines to Mainstreaming Gender in Teaching and Research were developed in RP2 through various pilot groups across all faculties, to facilitate the introduction of the gender perspective in all areas and disciplines of teaching and research. In RP3, the guidelines were published online, and physical copies printed. A total of 210 guides were disseminated across the different faculties of the university. In addition, the Guidelines have been translated into English, to facilitate its use by other universities across Europe and beyond.
- The [Felise Mentoring programme](#): the **FELISE (FEminist Leadership In ScienceE)** mentoring programme aimed at early career women researchers working in the GEP implementing institutions and wanting to pursue an academic career. These have been matched with senior researchers (tenured-track or permanent position) with Gender Equality awareness within their own institutions to discuss structural change.

e) Challenges

The limitations and challenges faced by the GEARING-Roles partners in their respective change processes are, in general, common to what is widely discussed among the structural change community (e.g. lack of Gender Equality budget; limited national policies; institutional inertia and non-prioritisation of Gender Equality) (Lombardo and Mergaert, 2013; Powell et al., 2018). In addition, attention should be given to new challenges evidenced by recent research on the integration of gender dimension in the content of research and innovation. The rise of anti-gender movements and their political agenda on education (Graff & Korolczuk, 2022; Revelles-Benavente & González Ramos, 2017), lobbying towards the suppression of gender perspective in teaching (Venegas, 2022), emerged as resistances in all educational levels including higher education (Heijstra & Pétursdóttir, 2023; Romero Gutiérrez, 2022). In addition, the consolidation of neoliberal management of universities is deepening gender inequalities in research and higher education institutions (Rosa & Clavero, 2021; Steinþórsdóttir et al., 2019). Gender biases in the evaluation of academic activity (research, teaching and knowledge transfer) (Gelber et al., 2022; Heijstra et al., 2017; López Díaz & Pereira, 2021) constitute an added obstacle to the achievement of equality but also to the recognition of feminised work such as the work for Gender Equality in the university (Pétursdóttir, 2017; Romero Gutiérrez, 2022).

In the particular case of GEARING-Roles, three limiting factors deserve attention as there are still few developments directed to avoid and tackle them. The first one refers to the contradictions and resistance arising from groups initially thought of as allies in the change processes. As it is the case in Spain, changes in national legislation have opened room for disagreements between trade unions and working groups responsible for Gender Equality work, generating not only delays in the process of approving GEPs, but also a sense of frustration and excessive use of time and energy in conflictive negotiation processes. This obligation to negotiate with trade union representatives for the approval of equality diagnoses and plans, with a strong focus on staff working conditions, is making it difficult to approve and register the plans and also to include in them aspects related to the student body or to issues inherent to the nature of a university, such as the introduction of the gender perspective in teaching and research, non-sexist communication or the public image of the institution. Secondly, the rise of anti-gender movements at international

but also national level that legitimises institutional resistance and inactivation to Gender Equality issues. This hinders the participation of gender experts at the forefront of equality plans as they are considered “too critical”, and institutions tend to assign gender-related work to more flexible and adaptable people. Finally, as a project scarred by the pandemic, the GEARING-Roles working groups have struggled disproportionately in terms of mental health and the burden of carrying out Gender Equality work in traditional institutional settings. While the personal costs of driving change-oriented initiatives have been widely discussed in the literature and communities of practice (see, e.g., Eyben and Turquet, 2013; Krook and Mackay, 2011), the pandemic has exacerbated a widespread sense of oppression, frustration, and lack of recognition of those responsible for advancing the agenda even in unfavourable scenarios. These were all significantly challenging circumstances faced by specific GEPI partners, but suffered by the project consortium as a whole, and recognisably also faced in other consortia.

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

The GEARING-Roles experience shows that drivers to institutional change are common across the different Gender Equality Plans (GEPs). At the contextual level, national legislation that binds institutions to implement GEPs and public resources for Gender Equality were identified as key to advance the equality agenda institutionally. In this sense, the participation in a H2020 project was a catalyst to initiate change processes, especially in institutions with no previous experience. At the general institutional level, the following points were identified as the main driving factors: (1) involvement of a wide range of actors representing different institutional layers and departments; (2) leadership commitment; (3) setting the GEP within the framework of broader institutional strategies and priorities; (4) internal institutional resources dedicated to Gender Equality; (5) capacity building; (6) using participatory and co-creative techniques throughout the whole process; and (7) a network of support and care.

3. Contact Point

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V. Case study 22: UNIC Alliance 2

1. Summary

At the end of 2018, the Erasmus University Rotterdam (EUR) had the lowest percentage of female full professors of all Dutch Universities (14,5%), while the lower levels of academic ladder were rather well gender balanced ([Women professors monitor, 2019](#)). EUR has agreed with the Ministry of Education, Culture and Science to achieve 25% female full professors by 2025. This agreement, and the lowest percentage of full professors, were the reason why EUR decided to adjust the [measure](#) already successfully used in Norway to promote gender equity in higher echelons, and called it 25/25 policy measure. The measure consisted of workshops, mentoring, portfolio preparations, confidential advice by an independent committee and financial support. It was open to all assistant and associate professors who aimed to be promoted to the next level with 1-3 years. In total 100 participants signed up, and 33 of the participants submitted the portfolio for a confidential advice. In the end, within a year, 9 women were promoted and 5 left the university for higher positions elsewhere. In 2022, EUR has achieved 25% of female full professors and has increased its target to 35% by 2025. Round 1 of the measure ran in 2020, and second round, called Beyond 2025 is starting in August 2023.

2. Description

a) Context

It is essential to design a measure that fits a particular organisation and its own challenges when it comes to gender equity. At EUR, the 'pipeline' was well filled, as on the level of PhD candidates and Assistant professors' gender disparity is not an issue. What we have seen as a challenge, was the progression of female talent to higher academic positions, namely to the level of Associate and Full professor.

It is also very important to have broad support for the measure. 25/25 policy measure was selected after numerous discussions with the Diversity and Inclusion team, HR policy, Academic Affairs, Faculty Diversity Officers, the Rector Magnificus and input from outside experts such as the HR team for Delft Technology Fellowship (Delft University) and Philip Eijlander Diversity Programme (University Tilburg), LNVH HR platform, and Professor Curt Rice, renowned expert in the field of Gender Equality in the workplace. All faculties of EUR Woudestein participated in the measure.

When the Executive Board gave a preliminary consent for the measure, chief diversity officer prof. Dr. Semiha Denktas then discussed this measure with all the deans of EUR to obtain their support. The measure has obtained the support of the deans and the definite approval from the Executive Board.

b) Objectives

The objective was to support achieving the target of at least 25% female full professors by 2025.

c) Implementation

The measure was launched in November 2019, and the applications for participation (via self-nomination or nomination) closed in January 2020. In the following months, 4 workshops were organised on the topics that participants themselves deemed important. Given that the Covid-19 outbreak has happened, the entire programme has been delivered online. Mentoring guidelines were provided for the mentors and mentees, and 3 portfolio preparation workshops were held (one for assistant professors, one for associate professors and one for the mixed group). The independent committee consisted of 3 members: one internal full professor and 2 external full professors. The independent committees were formed per department, and provided confidential feedback to the participants, which was based on comparing the portfolio to the participants' official faculty criteria for promotion. Possible advice was: ready for promotion, almost ready, or needs more time. Those with the latter two outcomes were eligible for financial support of max. €10,000, which was shared between the programme and the faculty. Individuals who received a positive, 'ready' advice, but were not promoted, were eligible for €5000 financial support from the 25/25 policy measure.

25/25 policy measure: round 1 2020/2021

Figure 1: overview of round 1 of 25/25 policy measure at Erasmus University Rotterdam

d) Successes

This measure knows successes at 2 levels:

1) Individual level

- a. More clarity for participants on where they are standing when it comes to career progression
- b. Peer to peer contact

- c. Access to faculty criteria for promotion
- d. Support to write their own portfolio
- e. Mentoring support

2) Systemic level:

- a. Awareness of (lack of) clarity of faculty criteria for promotion (as we had one or two cases where participants received a ready advice, nearly ready, and needs more time advice)-based on the same criteria, evaluated by 3 persons.
- b. Conversation with the deans, HR Business partners about the process surrounding promotion and clarity thereof

e) *Challenges*

It was a time consuming, and sensitive project to carry out, with a lot of stakeholders involved. Furthermore, independent committees were customised down to the department level, which involved a lot of administration and effort.

Once the participant received the advice, it was up to them to decide whether they wished to share it with their manager or a dean. Sometimes, receiving a positive independent result led to disappointment, as the positive advice was not internally followed up (advice was non-binding).

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

Recommendations are to dive into the clarity of the promotion criteria, and see whether they are clear, and objective. A suggestion was to include also 'soft' skills in the criteria, if employees were assessed on those (and we have received feedback that they were). Furthermore, more transparency of the promotion process is necessary, something Chief Diversity Officer and the project team have taken up with the deans and HR B partners. Last but not least, it is essential to monitor progression and obtain detailed insight into who is leaving the organisation, and for what reason, to be able to work on retention and promotion of (female) and other minoritized employees.

3. Contact Point

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4. References

<https://www.eur.nl/en/news/eur-nominated-010-inclusief-award-2525-initiative-ensure-growth-number-female-professors>

<https://www.eur.nl/en/about-eur/vision/inclusion-diversity-equity-access/initiatives/beyond-2525-towards-inclusive-academia>

W. Case study 23: UNITA Alliance

Mentoring programme in the Re-UNITA Project - UNITA Alliance

1. Summary

By endorsing the approach of "fixing the system not the women", Re-UNITA partners have promoted support action schemes not only for women researchers but also for men, both juniors and seniors (who are involved in selection committees and governing bodies).

A common mentoring programme has been implemented in each university of the Alliance, to support researchers especially during the early stages of their academic career, through the exchange with senior fellows that can give advices for successful career management and suggest strategies to overcome potential cultural and structural barriers. Once the mentoring programme was defined, all the mentors appointed in the respective universities have been invited to attend a European meeting in Turin, organised by UNITA, where they have defined a common approach to support their mentees.

After this first face-to-face event, regular online meetings have been organised (and are still being organised) for mentors, to encourage the sharing of their experiences with the mentees and to collect feedback from the ongoing mentoring process.

2. Description

a) Context

One of the 6 Re-UNITA partners, the University of Turin, is coordinating the four-year **MINDtheGEPs- Modifying Institutions by Developing Gender Equality Plans** – and particularly the **Research Centre for Women's and Gender Studies (CISRDe)**. Thanks to the expertise collected within this project funded by the EU research and innovation framework programme Horizon 2020's Science with and for Society funding scheme, the Re-UNITA project has implemented an ambitious and inclusive workplan dedicated to the gender balance in research careers.

Prof Cristina Solera (UNiTo), coordinating the MindtheGEPs project, is the leader of the Task 3.4 of Re-UNITA, dedicated to the gender balance in research career. This project's works has showed interesting information regarding a tool to tackle this issue: the mentoring.

On the basis of the experience of the MindTheGeps project and considering that our scope is centred in formal academic mentoring programmes, mentoring in academia can be envisaged as a relational structure which provides support and specific knowledge to develop a successful, independent academic career. On the basis also of the literature, effective faculty mentoring should involve both formal and informal relationships, including multiple "relationship constellations" distributed among different professional colleagues. It has been noted that academic mentors might cover three roles: teacher (that is, providing skills and knowledge closely related to their scientific work), sponsor (a facilitator of the mentee integration, who enhances their mentee visibility) and collaborator (the mentor can actively participate in the mentee research projects). Recent research has found that mentee who perceive their mentors as sponsors

are most successful (in terms of less time to reach tenure), especially if the mentors are also perceived as teachers. Furthermore, some authors described three support functions for the mentoring of doctoral students: psychosocial (referring to counselling, offering support role modelling), instrumental (giving challenging assignments, exposure) and networking. The literature has also pointed out that mentoring is indeed a powerful intervention for the development of junior academics, who can look forward to higher levels of well-being and better career outlooks, such as higher job satisfaction, self-efficacy, research productivity, less time to reach tenure.

b) Objectives

The Re-UNITA working group decided to design the characteristics of an effective mentoring to be implemented within the Re-Unita project. Again, with reference to the literature, amongst the best practices in faculty mentoring (including programme outline, and short- and long-term impacts), the key steps were chosen, as reported in the following list:

- Consulting junior and senior faculty, in order to identify the needs of all participants, assess the demographic groups and ensure they all have proper access to the mentoring programme;
- Identifying the structures, i.e., deciding which mentoring forms are most suited (for instance, skill acquisition usually lends itself more to workshops and seminars, while scholarly advice and support are more suited to one-to-one relationships and should be department-specific);
- Resources and tools available to provide mentors with training and incentives.

c) Implementation

This programme involves a mentoring relationship, during which each mentor will follow two mentees: monthly meetings are planned for each mentee, in-person or online at the participant's discretion (one individual meeting between mentor and individual mentees and one where each mentor will meet with both mentees, which also allows moments of peer-mentoring).

Matching has to be done following a transdisciplinary criterion, by pairing mentors and mentees who are not from the same research field, but rather belong to related scientific areas. This reduces possible conflicts of interest and encourage the creation of a separate and confidential space where it will be possible to discuss individual and institutional issues outside regular work relationships.

Orientation and training session for mentors and mentees in November 2022 has been planned: basics of mentoring have been further discussed by all mentors and mentees in separate groups. Participant's expectations and reflections have been collected, and contact between mentors and mentee formally initiated after the meeting.

Two monitoring and evaluation moments have been decided: they will be conducted during the programme through focus groups that have taken place in February 2023 (and during a second meeting tentatively scheduled in September 2023).

Key figures: More than 80 participants, 31 mentors and 50 mentees

Train the trainers: A workshop “Train the trainers” has been organised in Turin last beginning of October 2022 (both in presence and online), targeted mentors selected by each university, who have learned from experienced trainers the theoretical framework of gender issues in academic communities and practiced strategies to guide their mentees on how to manage potential cultural and structural barriers.

This event has been launched during the 2022 edition of the European Researchers' Night (30th September 2022) and for the first time the partners of UNITA Alliance have joined the force, by designing common formats and implementing joint public engagement activities in the framework of the project U*Night. During the Night the partners have organised a presentation of the mentoring programme in one of the common online formats (“A talk with young research!”). This action has brought high visibility to the initiative, as an UNITA good practice in the context of gender policies.

During the “Train the trainers” event, after a general introduction of the Re-UNITA project and of the mentoring programme, a brief presentation of the results of the analysis conducted by the partners regarding their Gender Equality policies has been reported. After this, the training on gender and science has followed: it has been conducted by experts in the field coming both from the University of Turin and from abroad with specific focuses onto situated knowledges for (i) implementing Gender Equality plans and (ii) transformative mentoring. Both focuses have been conducted with an informal approach and with team activities, in particular for the transformative mentoring, in which both mentors and mentees started to build up their ideas of mentoring.

d) Successes

Sharing practices and assessing the current state of gender balance in UNITA universities: the first success has been to tackle the question of gender balance in our universities. Thanks to a comprehensive survey regarding gender parity in our human resources, the mentoring programme has been built on a mutual knowledge of our universities regarding this question.

Interdisciplinary programme: The mentoring programme was built on an interdisciplinary basis. We noticed that both mentees and mentors were delighted to be able to exchange ideas and work with colleagues from different disciplines.

New kinds of social interaction: Beyond parity, mentoring helps to build “extraordinary” relationships. These informal relationships, built up gradually, can break down the isolation sometimes felt by researchers, especially younger ones. Especially in human sciences, we noticed that the mentees are gaining a lot of information through this one-to-one relationship.

e) Challenges

Seeking the help of already over-solicited female researchers: Within this mentoring programme, we looked for experienced female researchers to act as mentors. However, the pool of experienced, responsible female researchers is sometimes limited. As a result, these

researchers expressed a feeling of over-solicitation, which of course ran counter to the programme's objectives.

Adding value to participation: The programme wanted to put in place mechanisms to reward the participation of mentees and mentors. However, it is a difficult task, as participation and time limits are not precisely defined, and left to the free participation of mentors and mentees. This poses a particular difficulty with quantifying and anticipating the number of hours dedicated to this programme. One of the challenges is how to formalise participation in an activity that straddles the boundary between formal and non-formal.

Recruiting mentors and mentees: The above challenge has a concrete consequence: the difficulty of recruiting mentors and mentees for this scheme. In particular, how can we encourage participation in a transparent way? Participation procedures varied from one university to another. Broad calls for participation were shared by some universities. In others, in order to achieve a balance of profiles, it was decided to proceed more by co-optation.

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

Clarify the profile of participants, in particular whether partners want to follow a common procedure or not.

Provide a bibliography and clear recommendations to mentors on how to conduct a mentoring relationship.

Find ways of promoting participation that are adapted to each university and context.

Plan collective meetings in order to promote the participation in a collective programme and enhance interdisciplinary discussions on research careers.

3. Contact Point

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Clément Bardoux – Re-UNITA project manager – Université de Pau et des Pays de l'Adour – clement.bardoux@univ-pau.fr

4. References

Kick-off event flyer: <https://univ-unita.eu/Ficheiros/Sites/86/Eventos/1179/Re-UNITA%20Unight%20event.pdf>

Joint article Mindthegeps/Re-UNITA : <https://www.mindthegeps.eu/news/?tarContentId=10335>

Figure 1: Train the trainers event in Torino

X. Case study 24: UNIVERSEH Alliance

1. Summary

Among the 7 member universities of the Alliance, 5 of which are involved in Beyond UNIVERSEH, Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf (HHU) acts as a role model for the Alliance in dealing with Gender Equality issues. Indeed, with its wide-ranging and transversal action, the university addresses this issue from a number of angles and meets the standards set by the European Union through its Horizon Europe funding programme.

Although not all the measures adopted by HHU have yet been transposed at Alliance level, it is at the instigation of its German partners that the Alliance is going to set up an Ombudsperson. With the aim of raising awareness on the project and ensuring reporting processes are in place, an Ombudsperson position will be a new governance body of the UNIVERSEH Alliance.

2. Description

a) Context

HHU is a young and dynamic institution of higher education and research with a highly international profile situated in the heart of the European Union founded in 1965.

For more than 30 years, HHU has been developing its expertise in Gender Equality issues by drawing on and developing skills at the central level and also by relaying them to each faculty. The aim is to make Gender Equality a cross-cutting issue that is integrated into the institutional, cultural and teaching practices of the HHU.

All action to promote Gender Equality at HHU is steered by the Gender Equality office.

b) Objectives

The Gender Equality officer also called Equal opportunities officer and its team aim to advance and anchor measures and activities that promote equal opportunities at Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf.

c) Implementation

HHU has substantial resources for the implementation and monitoring of Gender Equality tasks.

HHU's equal opportunities team comprises 11 employees. This includes the Central Equal Opportunities Commissioner, who advises and assists university management in the enforcement of the legal requirements. In recent years, HHU has ensured that 9 of these 11 positions were made permanent to guarantee the continuity of Gender Equality measures currently in place and planning security for innovative new approaches in future Gender Equality work. To do so, HHU, as every university in North Rhine-Westphalia, can rely on a budget allocated by the Land for Gender Equality depending on the number of students.

A total of 24 decentralised equal opportunities officers have been appointed to support the equal opportunities work at the faculty level, with female employees working in the university's technical departments and administration as well as female students.

In practical terms, the centralised and decentralised action of the equal opportunities team will take shape at several levels:

- At individual level-Actions for researchers and professors
 - HHU has a Family Support Centre for students and employees of the university who wish to obtain advice and support on how to reconcile their family and professional lives. Among its many activities, the centre offers holiday camps. Additionally, the Equal Opportunities Office organises the national familifund programme, which supports young female academics.
 - HHU also offers workshops and trainings for women scientists, professors and students. The aim of these is to increase or strengthen the skills of participants.
 - Additionally, HHU also offers career and long-life coaching for female junior scientists (students or PhD students who wish to pursue their career in research), as well as individual coaching for professors.
- At institutional level
 - The Gender Equality framework plan and the Gender Equality plan for the faculties are institutional publications that set out the general framework for the institution, describe the obligations of staff (employees, employees with management duties, head of department) and define the actions to be implemented in terms of Gender Equality.
 - HHU has set up a gender monitoring system run by the department of financial planning and control, which collects and monitors data on the development of the gender balance in governance bodies, at various qualifications levels, as well as on staff.
 - HHU, through its department for personnel development, ensures that Gender Equality is taken into account during the selection of staff. This is achieved through a high degree of transparency, professionalised guidelines and templates, and standardised work processes (information materials can only be accessed via the intranet).
 - HHU provides measures against gender-based violence, particularly sexual harassment. To protect all employees and students who have been or are affected by acts of sexual nature, HHU has not only published Heinrich Heine University guidelines on dealing with sexualised discrimination and violence, but also set up a number of contact points for making complaints and seeking advice.
- At teaching level
 - Professorships of the women's and gender studies research network allows the integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content.

d) Successes

[Selma Mayer mentoring programme](#)

The SelmaMeyerMentoring programme is a staff development strategy for female researchers at the start of their career. It aims to help qualified, committed female early-career researchers identify and develop their skills and expertise, and systematically integrate these into their career planning.

This mentoring programme comprises a number of modules, including one-to-one mentoring, peer-group mentoring, skills workshops and networking.

Since it began in 2006, the programme has proven a resounding success: according to a recent study published by the Centre of Excellence Women and Science (CEWS), HHU ranks highly when it comes to increasing the proportion of women holding a professorship compared to 2012.

e) *Challenges*

To what extent will the UNIVERSEH Alliance be able to draw inspiration from HHU actions and transpose them to its research community?

f) *Recommendations on measures to be taken*

HHU draws on expertise developed over more than 30 years to implement its actions in the field of Gender Equality. The members of the Alliance are pragmatic and aware that not everyone will reach this level, particularly because the national and local financial resources required to implement this type of action are not the same for all partners.

Still, at the level of each individual institution, the partner universities can draw inspiration from the initiatives set up by HHU. In addition, the members of the Alliance are working collectively to ensure that the issue of Gender Equality and diversity is a cross-cutting priority for the consortium.

To date, this has involved the dissemination and sharing of good practice through themed staff weeks and diversity conferences/workshops for staff (researchers and administrative staff). Finally, the introduction of an ombudsperson in the second half of the implementation of the UNIVERSEH project will give institutional expression to this priority.

3. *Contact Point*

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CC UNIVERSEH Office: office@universeh.eu

4. *References*

<https://www.hhu.de/en/horizoneurope>

IV. Measures to ensure the mainstreaming of Gender Equality

A. Summary of findings

As a reader's digest, the richness and diversity of the 24 case studies is summarised in [Annex 1](#).

The main commonality between the different examples presented throughout this deliverable resides in the existence of a **Gender Equality Plan (GEP)**. This implies that the GEP is one of the primary components of any established strategy aiming at fostering change in terms of Gender Equality in research. Based on those GEPs, most universities/Alliances have developed committees, offices or programmes to tackle gender-related issues.

Another successful recurring activity is the **mentoring programme**, for example at the Heinrich Heine University Düsseldorf (member of the UNIVERSEH Alliance) or, at the Alliance level, through the RE-UNITA SwafS project (UNITA Alliance).

Other recurring activities are **courses, workshops and training** to raise awareness on gender imbalance as well as to develop new gender-sensitive perspectives in research.

Overall, the activities and actions implemented participated in **raising awareness among the research community** on these issues, while also **permitting female researchers to gain skills and training** so as to facilitate their **career progression**; for example, with the Akademe Programme at the University of the Basque Country (member of the ENLIGHT Alliance). Thus, the case studies presented here all highlight the importance of carrying out the work on these issues to **gradually implement change**.

However, a recurring issue underlined in many case studies concerns the **need to implement adequate and concrete measures** to succeed in implementing **systemic change**. Indeed, whether at the university or Alliance levels, it appears **difficult to keep the momentum and lead to profound transformations**. It was also pointed out that a majority of men remain in leadership position, while **women remain underrepresented**, despite the progress underlined. Moreover, in the case of Alliances, **dealing with various national legal frameworks and cultures increases the difficulty to implement concrete transformative measures**. Another point of improvement, as displayed in the cases of the GendER@UC project (University of Coimbra, member of the EC2U Alliance) and of the FilmEU Alliance, would be to **increase the involvement and participation of male researchers in these gender-related activities**.

Hence, the 24 case studies confirm the importance of **conducting concrete activities and implementing institutional policies** on Gender Equality in order to foster change. Awareness raising and training activities are essential in that regard. Furthermore, **identifying specific needs and taking into account a more intersectional conception** of Gender Equality are crucial to have a broader and deeper impact. The diversity of case studies presented here provide a large variety of perspectives to take stock of what is currently being done and what could be done in the future for improvement.

B. Possible measures

A majority of case studies outlined in this deliverable are examples of actions taken at the level of universities, with a minority presenting actions at Alliance level. This suggests that the good practices put forward here could be usefully **mainstreamed at Alliance level** to foster deeper impact and systemic change all over Europe.

To tackle the issue of identifying concrete measures that are needed to implement systemic change, one possible measure identified in several case studies would be to **systematically collect and analyse gender-disaggregated data**, in order to establish adequate and transformative measures. This would allow to set out relevant programmes, courses and training to progress in this area.

Moreover, to be able to reach out to the wider community, the **participation of male researchers** should be promoted through specific actions for men, that should be defined accordingly. Targeted training for those in management positions would also be relevant to foster systemic change. Additionally, encouraging bottom-up involvement is another way to engage the community as a whole.

Another measure to continue progressing in the area of gender mainstreaming would be to **establish long-term strategies, paired with long-term funding**, to ensure permeability and progress in all university areas. The continuous organisation of events as well as training and courses were underlined on several occurrences as being crucial elements to make a transformative impact.

Another way to ensure that progress is made is to **monitor and evaluate progress**. This can lead to taking additional actions to improve the work that has already been conducted. For instance, developing guidelines to implement measures and track progress, as it was accomplished in the GEARING Roles H2020 project by the University of Deusto (member of the UNIC Alliance), could help other universities and Alliances in developing or improving their own strategy.

FOREU2 Alliances are already reflecting together on Diversity and Equality within a working sub-group (chaired by the ENHANCE Alliance). Cross-Alliance collaborations could however be further developed; for example, organising **conferences and workshops between Alliances** would be another mean to make progress by sharing good practices.

Furthermore, when possible, **appointing one person responsible for the implementation of the Gender Equality strategy** at each university could help Alliances make rapid progress.

Moreover, **participating in European projects** is another way to ensure progress as it provides a framework and funds to advance in this area. Therefore, new projects could be dedicated to the specific development of programmes or training activities to foster these developments, notably at the level of Alliances.

Finally, the case studies detailed here can be used to reinforce and develop the Gender Equality Strategy of Alliances so as to ensure the mainstreaming of the gender dimension in R&I long-term strategies. Continuous work is needed to reach this objective, in order to make progress in this area by adopting adequate and relevant measures. Various actions and activities have

been identified in this deliverable that can serve as a basis for the future work of universities and Alliances in this area.

V. Annexes

Annex 1: Table summarising all case studies

Alliance/University	Description	Objectives	Successes	Challenges	Recommendations
Aurora, University of Iceland	Creation of an Equal Rights Committee	Support, implement and monitor Gender Equality policies	Programme on equality and diversity in research launched in fall 2023	N/A	N/A
Circle U. / University of Pisa	Gender Equality Plan / Equity and Diversity Office / free anti-violence Centre	Work-life balance, gender balance in leadership, Gender Equality in recruitment and career progression, measures vs. gender-based violence and sexual harassment, gender dimension integrated into research	Creation of the Equity and Diversity Office and of the free anti-violence Centre / allocation of 100 000€ in care activities / training courses	Institutionalisation of a teaching course on Gender Equality in local schools	Clearly identify programmes and missions to achieve the objectives / Clearly define roles and functions to make structural change
EC2U / University of Coimbra	European project GendER@UC	Promote Gender Equality in scientific research, mentoring and research career support, support career progression for women, develop inclusive research practices and	Raising awareness / high participation in activities	Increase male participation / evaluate impact on the work life of female researchers	Promote specific actions for men participation

		inclusive communication			
EELISA	EELISA Gender and Equality Working Group and its Gender Equality Plan in EELISA's SwafS project	Create a network of experts and practitioners sharing experience and best practices, and implement concrete actions / Gender Equality Plan: assessment of measures and data in the partner universities, implement actions at consortium level	Activities useful to create a network of practitioners	Difficult to keep the momentum / the collection of gender-disaggregated data was difficult	Need more analysis on the "whys"; differences in performance between partners, women less represented
ENHANCE	Mainstream inclusion, diversity and equality	Train the community for equality and promote those values in activities (short-term learning, public events and various resources)	Annual Diversity Report	Diverse situations in each partner country / Find the right communication channel at the university level	Involve the majority of the community / Encourage bottom-up involvement
ENLIGHT / University of the Basque Country	Akademie programme: training and support programme for female teachers and researcher	Empowerment process, acquire leadership skills, networks to share experience, identify needs for future programmes	6 editions, one per academic year; 600 female teachers/researchers have participated and acquired new skills	Detect specific needs and tools to overcome barriers	Implement those types of programmes to improve the number of women in leadership positions and reduce the salary gap

	s for career progression				
ERUA	Via Re:EURASwafS project; plan to mainstream Gender Equality	Map best practices and shared initiatives on the gender dimension, include the gender dimension in strategic documents, implementation of a Gender Equality Plan, organising joint training programmes, dedicated webpage, two-day seminar on Gender Innovation	Strategy ongoing so no successes yet	Different national frameworks so no homogenous gender policies at consortium level / need to find common action points to improve the gender balance	Appoint a contact person in each university that can be a support during a mobility (regarding gender-based violence) / implement targeted training sessions for university management positions / transparency / Creation of a Gender Index with measurement tools to track progress in member universities
EUNICE	Via REUNICE SwafS project; communication and dissemination activities, Diversity, Inclusiveness and Gender Equality Style Manual and the	Establish common criteria for communication, highlight the role in research of female researchers in EUNICE universities	Good reception of the manual / interest in the event	Issue with language while writing the Manual in English / Problem of binary limitation with male and female / difficulties with different cultural contexts	N/A

	International Day of Women and Girls in Science				
EURECA-PRO / Montanuniversität Leoben	Action Plan, Equality Plan, Diversity Plan	Promote a cooperative working atmosphere, provide equal opportunities	Activities add an impact on the university's culture of diversity and representation of women in all bodies / Regular activities and training courses organised / Offers counselling	Need to find the adequate measures to solve gender representation issues at the university; still an ongoing problem	Focus on gender mainstreaming in all aspects of university life / be more transparent in research sources and services to involve equally men and women in the decision-making process / guarantee equal pay + have regular gender audits / Create gender working groups and activities among students and staff
EURECA-PRO / University of Petrosani	Gender Equality Plan / Engaged at all level in Gender Equality	Eliminate discrimination for women in management structures / equal conditions of study, work and career advancement / inclusive and gender sensitive organisational climate / preventing harassment	Adoption of the strategy	Need for greater awareness / implement specific initiatives to solve the issue	Continue working on improving the strategy and actions being taken

<p>EURECA-PRO / Technical University of Crete</p>	<p>Gender Equality Plan based on the Horizon Europe and new framework for R&I of the Council of Europe</p>	<p>and gender discrimination Draw action plans for equality / promote equality and ensure it is guaranteed / training and mediation services / development of gender studies / studies and research related to gender issues / assist victims of discrimination / balanced personal and work life / reduce "glass ceiling" phenomenon</p>	<p>Creation of a Gender Equality Group by the students</p>	<p>Administrative staff still mostly female; need actions to change bias and stereotypes in work categories</p>	<p>Collect data on positions of responsibility to be able to find adequate measures to solve issues</p>
<p>EURECA-PRO / Silesian University of Technology</p>	<p>Gender Equality Plan with creation of a dedicated team; collection of data then development of adequate activities</p>	<p>promote an organisational structure that respects gender balance / support for balance between career and family life / increase gender balance in decision making bodies and processes / equal access to recruitment</p>	<p>Various internal legal acts on Gender Equality / implementation of policies against discrimination</p>	<p>Different types of expectations regarding Gender Equality; complex situation to address / lack of knowledge of university's structures to counteract discrimination</p>	<p>N/A</p>

		and career development / integrate the gender dimension in research courses and training / countering issues of gender-based violence, incl. sexual harassment			
EURECA-PRO / University of León	Equality Plan with the creation of an "area of social responsibility" and an "equality unit"	Collect data / raise awareness / advance communication / guarantee equality in recruitment and promotion / work/life balance / participation of women in university life / prevent harassment / fight against violence / risk assessment employment with a gender perspective	Number of activities that have increased equality through the Equality Plan and Equality Unit	Make change at all levels of the institution / develop courses on Gender Equality and issues	Continue to develop actions with a long-term perspective / assuring quality and permeability to all academic stages and areas of knowledge
FilmEU	Plan to implement a more ambitious training programme for Gender Equality (already include the	Encourage FilmEU_RIT researchers to train on the gender dimension in research / ensure that the community is more aware of the gender	Training with experts available for the project's researchers	Less engagement of male researchers in training opportunities	Secure funding to develop Alliance-level training / work with experts and other Alliances / monitor the number of researchers

	gender dimension in research)	dimension to inform research and the preparation of application for future projects			who have been trained
NeurotechEU	The Alliance prioritises Gender Equality	Foster Gender Equality for equitable workforce and sustainable growth	"Women in NeurotechEU" event	Issue of the gender gap in the STEM field of higher education that roots deeper and complex to overcome	Encourage women to engage in the STEM field through programmes, activities or events and foster their career development
NeurotechEU / The Bogazici University	Systems and governance structures implemented to advance Gender Equality	Equal representation in research teams and labs / training / incorporate gender issues in research and teaching / training in gender-sensitive teaching techniques	Women's Studies Centre (conferences, seminars, workshops on Gender Equality, women's rights and feminist theory) / Gender Studies Programme / Support and Counselling Services / Student Clubs and Organisations / Training and workshops	Women remain underrepresented in leadership positions	Develop Gender Equality Plans / raise awareness / provide training / integrate gender perspectives in research and gender balance in decision making bodies / collect and analyse gender disaggregated data / monitor and evaluate progress
NeurotechEU / Radboud University	Diversity, Equity and Inclusion (DEI) as crucial	Drive change via changes in policy with practice tools / monitoring /	Creation of a DEI Office / awareness increased / Increasing	Gender related to social categories and issue	Continue actions / Implement policies / Provide

	principles; inclusive campus	Implement policies and procedures / accessible, inclusive and safe campus	women presence in higher position in research / DEI Unconscious Bias Theatre Workshops	with binary vision of gender; need to recognise intersectionality	support / Raise awareness / strengthen leadership skills and knowledge through studies and training
NeurotechEU / University of Lille	Support Gender Equality via various systems and governance arrangements; based on national principles for the education system	Reduce inequalities by taking into account that it is the result of multiple factors	Increased awareness / positive implication of the community / successful policy integration and alignment / "University with a big 'she'" event	Lack of gender-disaggregated data / underrepresentation of women in leadership positions / unconscious bias / insufficient gender expertise and knowledge / limited institutional support and resources	Collect gender disaggregated data and monitor + evaluate the data / establish gender-responsive funding mechanisms / monitor and evaluate progress with targets and indicators
RUN-EU	Establishment of a Gender and Diversity Ambassador Network (GDA)	Ensure equal distribution of resources and power / equal possibilities in R&I	Fostered a culture of awareness and understanding / Strengthening of human capital resources in R&I	Improve best practices sharing within the consortium / difficulty to have a long-term strategy but ongoing commitment needed	Promoting research opportunities in the field of gender diversity and increase women participation / Integrate gender and diversity in as much training materials as possible
Transform4Europe /	Gender Equality	Attract the whole research	Funds allocated for	Need more communication	Awareness raising and

University of Silesia	Plan activities: call for the best thesis on themes of equality and diversity + internal research excellence initiative grant competition	community at different career levels to conduct excellent research in gender and diversity areas	research on gender issues	on and awareness raising to involve the whole community / limited interest because lack of specialists in the subject	communication important to have active participation of the community
UNIC / University of Deusto	GEARING Roles H2020 Project	2 events organised by UNIC / Project aimed at challenging and transforming gender roles linked to professional careers and reach institutional change	Awareness raising / Many activities / Deusto Guidelines for gender mainstreaming in teaching and research / Mentoring programme	Limited budget and national policies / Persistence of gender bias / resistance to change from certain groups / difficulties to advance the agenda	Participation in H2020 project helps initiate change
UNIC / Erasmus University Rotterdam	Increase percentage of female full professors via workshops, mentoring, portfolio preparations, advice by independent committee	Have at least 25% of female full professors by 2025	Individual level: support for portfolio and clear criteria for promotion and career progression / Systemic level: awareness of lack of clarity for promotion and talks with governance bodies to	Needs a lot of administrative effort / non-binding project so not all were promoted	Have clear promotion criteria / transparency on the promotion process / monitor progression

	and financial support		improve clarity		
UNITA	Mentoring programme in the RE-UNITA SwafS project; common to all UNITA universities	Support researchers in the early stages of their academic careers	Assessment of the state of gender balance within the Alliance / Interdisciplinary programme	Seeking help of oversolicited female researchers / add value to participation / recruiting mentors and mentees	Clarify the profile of participants / provide clear recommendations to mentors on how to conduct a mentoring relationship / find way to promote participation / plan collective meetings to enhance interdisciplinary discussions on research careers
UNIVERSEH / Düsseldorf University	Activities of the university in terms of Gender Equality used for the Alliance	Gender Equality Office aim to advance measures and activities to promote equal opportunities at HHU	Mentoring programme for female early career researchers	How to integrate the activities of HHU into the Alliance	Share good practices between members of the Alliance via conferences and workshops / Appoint a person responsible for the implementation of the Gender Equality strategy at the level of the Alliance

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